

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

D1.7 Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results v1.0

Document Summary Information

Grant Agreement No	951867	Acronym	5G Routes
Full Title	Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results v1.0		
Start Date	01/09/2020	Duration	36 months
Project URL	https://www.5g-routes.eu		
Deliverable	D1.7		
Work Package	WP1		
Contractual due date	30.11.2020	Actual submission date	30.11.2020
Nature	R	Dissemination Level	PU
Lead Beneficiary	VTT		
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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No 951867

Revision history (including peer reviewing & quality control)

Version	Issue Date	% Complete	Changes	Contributor(s)
v0.1	24.9.20	0	Initial Deliverable Structure	J. Scholliers
v0.2	2.10.20	10%	first content based on telco feedback	J. Scholliers
v0.3	8.10.20	20%	content added based on telco feedback	J. Scholliers
v0.4	22.10.20	30%	content added after telcos	J. Scholliers, P. Durkin, C. Skoufis
v0.5	5.11.20	50%	content added after telcos	J. Scholliers, C. Skoufis, L. Nykänen, A. Levinskis
v0.6	11.11.20	70%	content added after telco	J. Scholliers, All contributors
v0.7	13.11.20	80%	content added after telco	J. Scholliers, S. Nikolaou
v0.8	19.11.20	90%	version for peer review	J. Scholliers
v0.9	27.11.20	99%	comments of peer reviewers M. Krupp (TELIA) and J. Montesa (BRA) integrated and final input	J. Scholliers
v1.0	30.11.20	100%	Final version	J. Scholliers

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
5G	5th generation
5G-PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
ADAS	Advanced Driver Assistance Systems
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
CBA	Cost-Benefit Analysis
CCAM	Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport System
C-V2X	Cellular Vehicle-to-Everything
DbW	Drive By Wire
DDS	Data Distribution Service
E2E	End-to-End
ECU	Electronic Control Unit
eMBB	enhanced Mobile BroadBand
ERTMS	European Rail Traffic Management System
EU	European Union
FOT	Field Operational Test
FRMCS	Future railway mobile Communication System
GA	Grant Agreement
gNB	Next Generation NodeB
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
GSM-R	Global System for Mobile Communication - Railways
HMD	Head Mounting Device
HW	Hardware
ICS	Intersection Controller System
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
IoT	Internet Of Things
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LIDAR	Light Detection And Ranging
MAMCA	Multi-Actor Multi-Criteria Analysis
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
mMTC	massive Machine Type Communications
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
MOS	Mean Opinion Score
MOS-AVQO	Mean Opinion Score - Audio Visual Quality Objective
MOS-AVQS	Mean Opinion Score - Audio Visual Quality Subjective
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
NTP	Network Time Protocol

Abbreviation / Term	Description
OBD	On-Board Diagnostics
OBU	On Board Unit
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
PLMN	Public Land Mobile Network
PR	Penetration Rate
PTP	Precision Time Protocol
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RSU	Road Side Unit
RTK	Real Time Kinematics
RTT	Round Trip Time
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
SLAM	Simultaneous Localization And Mapping
SUS	System Usability Scale
SW	Software
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats
T&L	Transport and Logistics
UC	Use Case
UE	User Equipment
UHD	Ultra High Definition
URLLC	Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications
V2D	Vehicle-to-device
V2G	Vehicle-to-grid
V2I	Vehicle-to-Infrastructure
V2N	Vehicle-to-network
V2P	Vehicle-to-pedestrian
V2V	Vehicle-to-vehicle
V2x	Vehicle-to-everything
VR	Virtual Reality
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
VS	Visualisation System

1 Executive Summary

The 5G-ROUTES project will conduct advanced field trials of most representative and innovative CCAM applications seamlessly functioning across a designated 5G cross-border corridor (Riga-Valga-Tallinn-Helsinki) spanning across 3 EU member states borders (Latvia-Estonia-Finland) in order to validate the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications under realistic conditions, so as to accelerate the widespread deployment of 5G E2E interoperable CCAM ecosystems and services in digitized motorways, railways and shipways throughout Europe.

The scope of this deliverable is to define the methodology and the toolset for both the technological performance and business validation of the use cases. This deliverable gives the state of the test framework at the current state of the project (end of month 3 of implementation). The use cases and the selection of the trial locations are not yet finalized. An updated version of this deliverable will be provided in month 10, and will include more details, including the common logging format as well as the procedures for collecting data. The final version of this report (deliverable D1.8, due in month 24) will consolidate insights from the first phase of the large scale trials execution, providing a reference framework for CCAM services validation.

The report gives an overview of the testing framework. The testing framework builds on the expertise and the results of other projects, such as 5G-SOLUTIONS, 5G-TOURS, TRUSTS, FESTA and 5G-MOBIX. 5G-ROUTES uses the iterative Plan-Do-Check-Act approach, including 3 cycles for the technical validation, with 2 local trial cycles for 3GPP R16 and R17 and one wider large scale trial cycle covering the whole corridor. The performance KPIs of each use case will be evaluated during the different testing cycles, to illustrate how 5G capabilities and 5G-Routes technical enablers are leveraged and how they impact application performance. Testing of CCAM automated driving use cases puts specific requirements to the testing environment. The local trials will be performed near the border crossing between Estonia-Latvia and on the ferry between Tallinn and Helsinki. In addition, tests will be performed at the Bikernieki racing track in Riga, where a virtual border involving Estonian and Latvian MNOs will be set up.

The business validation process is challenged with engaging and examining the field Trials with a commercial and business lens in order to identify those solutions that are most likely to become commercially viable and can deliver the most immediate quantifiable value to the stakeholders involved in each Use Case. The business validation process in 5G-ROUTES is based on the approach used in the 5G-SOLUTIONS project. 5G-ROUTES uses a methodology based on the Lean Start-up methodology, in 4 phases: customer validation, solutions alignment, business model selection and growth trajectory. The Business impact assessment of 5G-ROUTES will be based on the analysis of the business models and value propositions through the application of the - adapted to the project needs – Multi-Actor Multi-Criteria Analysis (MAMCA) methodology that will result to a broad screening of the business opportunities and their ranking, followed by a Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) that will evaluate in-depth the present value of the benefit streams for the selected business cases

Further the report describes the data collection. Starting from an initial list of the KPIs, the components where data is collected are defined. For the technical validation, data will be collected from the network, vehicles and from the other equipment used in the project. End-users will be involved for some use cases for user acceptance evaluation. A uniform format for data collection will be defined. The collected data will be uploaded to the Tenant Web, where the KPIs will be visualised. The different methods and tools for collecting information from end-users are described.

Core to this deliverable is the structure of the test plan, which will be developed for all use cases prior to starting the evaluation. Last, D1.7 describes how the different use cases plan to perform testing and provides the conclusions to be considered for the next steps of the project implementation.

2 Introduction

The 5G-ROUTES project will conduct advanced field trials of most representative and innovative CCAM applications seamlessly functioning across a designated 5G cross-border corridor (Riga-Valga-Tallinn-Helsinki) spanning across 3 EU member states borders (Latvia-Estonia-Finland) in order to validate the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications under realistic conditions, so as to accelerate the widespread deployment of 5G E2E interoperable CCAM ecosystems and services in digitized motorways, railways and shipways throughout Europe.

The scope of this deliverable is to define the methodology and the toolset for both the technological performance and business validation of the use cases.

2.1 Mapping 5G ROUTES Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map 5G ROUTES's Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1. Adherence to 5G ROUTES's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

5G ROUTES GA Component Title	5G ROUTES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D1.7	<i>Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results v1.0</i>	<i>This document</i>	
TASKS			
<i>T1.4 Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results</i>	<i>The testing framework will entail acceptance test procedures for conducting both the technological and business validation of the use cases considering the associated service management.</i>	<i>Section 3.3, 3.4</i>	<i>High level description of the technological and the business validation framework</i>
	<i>The testing framework will entail acceptance test procedures for conducting both the technological and business validation of the use cases considering the associated service management.</i>	<i>3.4, 4</i>	<i>Section 3.4 describes business validation acceptance tests; quality of technical performance tests is addressed in chapter 4</i>

5G ROUTES GA Component Title	5G ROUTES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
	<i>In particular, as far as the technological validation is concerned, we will define the procedures for collecting the data feeds from the 5G nodes, stating also how these feeds will be used and analysed by the Tenant Web Portal to produce and present the KPI values in a graphical form.</i>	3.5, 4	<i>Section 3.5 gives an overview of the data collection process; chapter 4 discusses data collection processes</i>
	<i>Threshold limits for the benchmarking of the results will also be defined per target KPI based on the requirements stemming from each CAM use case.</i>	N/A	<i>Target values for the KPIs are discussed in D1.1.</i>
	<i>The methodology will also define how the interaction with the CAM end-users will be achieved taking into consideration the specificities of task T1.1.</i>	4.4	<i>Chapter 4.4. discusses the Interaction with end-users during technical performance and business validation.</i>
	<i>For the business validation we will use the lean start-up methodology that centres around the main motivations of a business.</i>	3.4	<i>Business validation methodology is described in 3.4</i>
	<i>The inputs will include apart from the business case itself, end-user feedback from their direct engagement in the field trials of the vertical use cases.</i>	3.4, 4.4	
	<i>The corresponding outputs will be validations that will allow to identify those use cases that have the highest commercialisation potential so as to progress to the next step of creating a service product portfolio.</i>	3.4	

5G ROUTES GA Component Title	5G ROUTES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
	<i>For this purpose, we will use a set of questionnaires, surveys and focused group workshops directly engaging also the customers of the CAM consortium partners</i>	N/A	<i>Not yet available, as dependent on the use cases, which will be described in D1.1. Questionnaires, surveys and workshop material for business validation will be included in D5.1.</i>
	<i>A detailed set of metric parameters considered for the business validation of each use case will be developed, which will be interrogated and quantified as part of the business validation process with the CAM end-users</i>	N/A	<i>A draft set is described in section 4.2, but the final set not yet available, as dependent on the use cases, which will be described in D1.1. Questionnaires, surveys and workshop material for business validation will be included in D5.1.</i>

2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

2.2.1 Relation to other deliverables

This deliverable describes the assessment framework, addressing both technical performance evaluation and business validation. Figure 1 shows the relation between the work described in this deliverable and the other project deliverables.

The work builds on the work of Deliverables D1.1, D1.3 and D1.5. Deliverable D1.1 describes the use cases, scenarios and KPIs are defined. Deliverable D1.1 will discuss the KPI for both technical, service and business values, and their target values. Deliverable D1.3 describes the 5G network requirements, architecture and the deployment in the trial sites. Deliverable D1.5 analyses how the use cases benefit from 5G, describes the KPIs and the test measurements.

From D1.1, the specific features of use cases, such as the components required, situational variables and possibility to involve test users, are to be taken into account when designing the methodology. The KPIs affect the network requirements, and hence the 5G functionalities which will be included in the 5G test network at the trial sites. This work will be described in D1.3. The network architecture and its deployment in the test site affects to the test scenarios, and also to the test framework. D1.5 describes how the KPIs have to be measured.

The output of this work will be used to develop the test plans, which will be described in D4.1, and also supports the business validation work, which will be reported in D5.1, as well as the impact assessment, which will be described in D5.3.

An important aspect of the technical evaluation is the data collection. This report will provide requirements for the data collection, which will be input to the Tenant Web report D2.7.

Figure 1. Relation between this deliverable and the other deliverables

Figure 2 shows the timeline of this report and the related deliverables. This report provides the first version of the testing framework. At the moment of writing, the work on the specification of the use cases (D1.1), the deployment plans for the trial site networks (D1.3) and the specification of the KPIs and their measurements (D1.5) is still going on, and hence this document is a living document, which will be updated in the coming months. Work will continue in the beginning of 2021 with, among others, the selection of the final sites for the trials, the specification of a common data format for the evaluation data and the procedures for uploading the data. This work will be reported in an updated version of this deliverable (in M10), to be ready by June 2021, and will serve as input for the work in D4.1. The procedures mentioned in this report including the data collection procedures will be tested during the lab trials, reported in D3.8. The results of the lab trials will be reported in D3.8. The assessment framework will then be used for the first evaluation runs during the localized large-scale trials. The procedures may then be refined based on the experiences during the evaluation, reported in D4.6. The specifications of the different data collection procedures will then be reported in the final version of the assessment framework, in August 2022.

Figure 2. Timeline of the deliverables related to this report.

2.2.2 Deliverable structure

As stressed in the previous paragraph, this document is based on draft descriptions of the use cases and scenarios and on a draft deployment plan at the trial sites.

In chapter 3, first an overview of relevant work on assessment frameworks which has been performed in other relevant frameworks, on which the work will be developed.

Based on this work, a high-level outline of the testing framework is described for both the technical performance evaluation procedures, business validation, addressing also the data collection and KPI visualization procedures. Especially CCAM automated driving use cases set requirements to the development and testing environment, which have to be taken into account during testing and data collection.

Chapter 4 discusses the data collection. Although the use cases are not yet completely defined, and the list of KPIs is still provisional, reflections on made on the methods for collecting the data.

Chapter 5 gives a general overview of the test plan, which will be elaborated in more detail in D4.1, prior to starting the actual trials.

Chapter 6 gives an overview of the different use cases, which data will be collected, where they will be tested and if test users will be involved.

Chapter 7 draws the conclusions of this report, indicates the next steps towards the assessment and the requirements to the data collection system.

3 Testing framework overview

This section will give an overview of the framework. The chapter starts with an overview of related projects, which serve as background for the work, described in this deliverable

3.1 Related work

The testing framework will leverage, enhance and optimise the frameworks for the validation and benchmarking of results from previous relevant projects. The following relevant projects are described:

- 5G-SOLUTIONS [3], a 5G-PPP project using a testing framework based on the Deming's Plan-Do-Check-Act cycle [2],
- 5G-TOURS [4] and 5G-EVE [5], 5G-PPP projects,
- 5G-MOBIX [6], a 5G-PPP project on cross-border CCAM,
- FESTA [7]
- TRUSTS [8], a H2020 project using the same iterative approach as 5G-ROUTES.

3.1.1 5G-SOLUTIONS

5G-SOLUTIONS is a 5G-PPP project, which develops realistic, advanced and business relevant innovative use cases in five key vertical industries by developing and providing a representative set of detailed use case scenarios with appropriate metrics to test and validate the performance characteristics of 5G. The Deming's Plan-Do-Check-Act is the fundament for Living Lab iterations.

3.1.1.1 Business Validation

A subgroup of the 5G-PPP Infrastructure Association (BVME) published an initial white paper [1] in June 2020 which discusses a broad methodology for business validation in 5G vertical use cases. The methodology proposes a Lean Start-up approach to assessing user needs and aligning potential commercialisation of outputs from the research project that are customer oriented, validated and supported by commercially motivated consortium partners. The methodology is initially defined and applied in 5G-SOLUTIONS (<https://www.5gsolutionsproject.eu>) and the White Paper also intersects findings from other ICT-17 and ICT-19 projects which are also attempting to identify a consistent approach to business validation in 5G verticals.

Figure 3. Business Validation Methodology for 5G Verticals

The central tenant of the White Paper proposes that there are four phases which are almost always present in some form in assessing viability for vertical use cases (Figure 3). The figure also illustrates that technological

validation, the other pillar of validation in 5G-PPP projects, is a parallel activity to business validation and the processes are intertwined and complimentary. Section 3.4 describes a derivate of this initiative which will be implemented within 5G-ROUTES.

3.1.1.2 Technical performance assessment

In 5G-SOLUTIONS, end users are able to perform advance technological and business validation of highly and innovative and future oriented use cases in near real-time. Technical and business validation goes hand in hand, starting with templates for the business validation before the technological validation, focusing on methods for confirming that there is a real business value. The following topics should be assessed in the technological test and validation process:

- Array of test cases/scenarios and test types covered;
- Different test types and different testing tool types applied;
- Test architecture and systems for visualization of data applied;
- Use of automatically execution of test cases;
- Use of acceptance testing methods. The types of acceptance testing methods are:
 - “Factory acceptance” testing (Alfa testing) for whether or not a component or system satisfies requirements including hardware and/or software.
 - “User acceptance testing (Beta testing) for tests whether the user accepts the solution.
 - “Operational testing “for tests whether processes and procedures are in place and allows a system to be used and maintained, e.g. training, security etc.,
 - “Contract and regulation testing for testing whether a system meets governmental, legal and safety standards.

Figure 4. Overall testing and validation process in 5G-SOLUTIONS

Four key phases in testing have been identified and described:

- Test analysis and design phase, concentrating on extracting the test objectives, mapped KPIs and conducting a requirement traceability and testability assessment.
- Test specification phase: translating the use case scenarios into an executable specification format

- Test setup and execution, consisting of the following process steps: select testing tools and system under test (SUT) based on the test case; deploy testing tools and SUT; configure the test environment based on the test case and type; execute tests; collect test data.
- Performance Evaluation and lessons learned.

3.1.1.3 KPI visualization

According to 5G-ROUTES agreement, one of the project’s objectives is to exploit and extend an asset (KPI visualisation system) from the 5G-SOLUTIONS project [3] to produce the Tenant Web Portal for facilitating the parallel execution of the use cases and the validation of key target KPIs in real-time whilst being in the field.

EBOS, who is also participating to 5G-SOLUTIONS consortium, will leverage the KPI visualisation system (VS) and along with 5G-ROUTES partners, will extend its functionality to cover multi-tenancy in the cloud, the cross-border context and the additional KPIs in each of the use cases. Since the 5G-SOLUTIONS project is on-going (the project started on 1.7.2019), a new instance of the KPI VS, will be created in order to be utilised as the Tenant Web Portal, for the 5G-ROUTES. As previously mentioned, the necessary software adaptations will be developed to the KPI VS to produce the Tenant Web Portal.

Below we are presenting an overview of the 5G-SOLUTIONS KPI VS, as extracted from the publicly available deliverable D3.1B [14] “KPI Visualisation System Specifications and Design (v2.0)”, as submitted on April 2020.

Figure 5. 5G-SOLUTIONS KPI Visualisation System Design

The KPI VS enables the automation and acceleration of the analysis of the test cases results, provides a graphical representation to the end user, while also including a user management module for controlling the access rights of the users to the data of each use case. The KPI VS employs numerous modules (data collector, real-time data processor, ML optimizer and graphical user interface) to process the information ingested from the 5G facilities and UC applications and make it available through the Web. The components of the KPI VS deployed on the cloud, the different modules of the visualisation system will be placed, to provide scalability and elasticity. The

user interface (UI) design and implementation follows the user interface design principles with focus on how to satisfy various types of users by providing a smooth, easy and nice user experience. A sample design of the KPI VS is presented in Figure 5, where is shown that the dashboard-concept has been followed with information to be grouped in sections (widgets), a number of graphs are presenting network and application data as KPIs, and filtering controls are filtering the presented data. The same approach will also be followed to 5G-ROUTES.

3.1.2 5G-TOURS and 5G-EVE

5G-TOURS is a 5G-PPP project, aiming to demonstrate the 5G network's ability to support diverse requirements on the same infrastructure at a large scale, by providing efficient and reliable close-to-commercialisation services for citizens and tourists in three different cities: Athens, Rennes and Turin. D7.1 presents the basic version of the 5G-TOURS evaluation methodology which guides the pilot sites during all the steps of KPI validation process including: pilot test case design and definition, test case execution, data collection, data analysis and finally evaluation against predefined KPI targets. It provides the basic building blocks for the 5G-TOURS evaluation methodology, dealing with the evaluation of the network KPIs: latency, throughput, reliability, density, mobility, coverage, slice deployment time, security and location accuracy.

To meet the aforementioned requirement the 5G-TOURS project adopts as the baseline methodology the Model-based Testing and Validation Methodology designed and developed in the 5G-PPP Phase 3 project 5G EVE. The workflow of evaluation methodology adopted both in 5G-EVE and 5G-TOURS projects is illustrated in Figure 6.

In 5G-TOURS, the terminology used in the 5G EVE for testing and validation methodology is reused. The main target of the evaluation methodology is to provide the appropriate guidelines to the pilot sites in order to design the test cases, to prepare the tests, to execute and finally evaluate the test results. Independently of low-level conditions, requirements, etc., the high-level workflow for the evaluation process, consists of the four phases: a) Test Design; b) Test Preparation; c) Test Execution and Monitoring and; d) Results Analysis and Evaluation.

Figure 6. 5G-TOURS evaluation process workflow

Test Design

The first step toward the evaluation is to understand what the Vertical needs concerning trial execution in 5GTOURS pilot sites and design a set of pilot tests. The main goal of the Test Design phase is to permit the developers of the trials to understand the objectives of the different experiments, how they can be executed, and what KPIs are critical for the evaluation process. Starting from a pilot test plan template, low-level test plans are generated which translate the vertical requirements into specific service descriptors, test descriptor and test scripts.

Test Preparation

The objective of this phase is to get everything ready to execute the desired trials. All trials have some initial conditions that must be set up, and most of them have some variables and threshold values for validation that verticals may want to particularize. This customization enables the generation of the required descriptors and blueprints (templates).

Test Execution and Monitoring

Once the entire infrastructure is ready, the virtual environment (e.g. virtual machines, containers, VNFs) to run the pilot tests is built and configured. This should be done automatically, and when ready, the experimenters can start executing the different trial test cases. Both application and infrastructure metrics are gathered and made available both for monitoring (visualization) and for validation purposes.

Result Analysis and Evaluation

Results are collected and analysed, and the final evaluation report is generated. There are many levels of analysis, depending on many occasions on the KPIs which are of interest for each specific vertical. A set of network KPIs are measured by default by 5G-TOURS as it will be based on the 5G EVE platform, in order to validate the results against the 5G-PPP KPIs and as a way to ensure that the obtained results are valid.

3.1.3 5G-MOBIX

5G-MOBIX aims to showcase the added value of 5G technology for advanced CCAM use cases and validate the viability of the technology to bring AD to a high level of vehicle automation (SAE Level 4 and above). To do this, 5G-MOBIX will demonstrate the potential of various 5G features on real European roads and highways and create and use sustainable business models to develop 5G corridors, with particular emphasis on seamless service provisioning across borders. In this effort, 5G-MOBIX will utilize and upgrade existing key assets (infrastructure, vehicles, components) and further ensure the smooth operation and co-existence of 5G within a heterogeneous environment comprised of multiple incumbent technologies such as ITS-G5 and C-V2X. CCAM use cases and the expected benefits of 5G will be tested during trials on 5G corridors in different EU countries as well as in Turkey, China and Korea.

The great challenge in the deployment of the use cases in cross-border locations is to deal with the effects of roaming/ handover processes to get a timely, continuous and seamless operation of the corresponding CCAM applications. In this sense, it is the design of the architecture of the user stories which is conditioning the appearance of the particular cross-border issues. The goal of the Technical Evaluation is to analyse the different implementations of these cross-border mobility solutions provided by the trial sites involved in the Project and validate them for automated driving. 5G-MOBIX employs two types of trial sites in order to cover a wide range of scenarios and implementations of the user stories, namely, the cross-border corridor trial sites and the local trial sites. In the framework of 5G-MOBIX, four different categories of cross-border issues were identified (D2.1 and D2.2): telecommunication, application, security & data privacy, and regulation.

5G-MOBIX has defined list of technically related KPIs grouped into two main areas: general KPIs, devoted to qualifying 5G as the core connectivity infrastructure for CCAM, and handover KPIs, more explicitly focused on the cross-border mobility performance. The technical evaluation methodology will serve the following high-level objectives:

- Assess network capabilities in a use case-agnostic manner, contributing to the understanding of the baseline performance of the network, orthogonal to application specificities and performance requirements. The evaluation methodology aims at both data and control plane performance:
 - *Data plane*: network capabilities will be assessed on both an end-to-end and a per network segment basis.
 - *Control plane*: a detailed assessment of events/states and transitions will enable the finer-grained, explicit look at cross-border issues e.g., roaming latency.
- Assess user perceived performance on an end-to-end basis, in a use case specific manner. This will allow the assessment of the impact of cross-border mobility on CCAM application-level.

The purpose of 5G-MOBIX Impact Assessment is to assess the impacts of seamless service provisioning across borders from a socio-economic perspective. To this end, a specific set of metrics is targeted for quality of life (in terms of personal mobility, traffic efficiency, traffic safety and the environment) and business impacts. The main objectives of the 5G-MOBIX impact assessment are:

- Explore how 5G-MOBIX systems can affect quality of life, in terms of personal mobility, traffic efficiency, traffic safety and the environment
- Evaluate how the cooperation between the stakeholders and trial sites in the project has contributed to the development of new innovations and business models and (future) deployment of solutions
- Assess the costs and benefits of 5G-MOBIX solutions from the perspectives of the society, innovation ecosystems and individual businesses.

The objective of the technical evaluation is to produce the relevant KPIs values. During the execution of the relevant user stories in the trials, numerous measurements will be performed. Once the measurements are made, the KPIs can be calculated. Based on standard and established conformance and interoperability testing methodology [13] one of the first steps is to identify the potential location of *Points of Control and Observation* in the system under test where measurements will be taken. Data is collected in an agreed format. The data processing step, consists of taking the formatted data and applying a set of filtering and processing calculations to obtain the targeted KPIs. This will be done using data processing tools and scripting languages, and specific attention will be paid on the events, states and transitions of the system due to mobility, in the targeted handover scenarios.

3.1.4 FESTA

FESTA is a methodology developed in several H2020 funded projects for the evaluation of FOTs (Field Operational Tests) and is the basis for the Common Evaluation Methodology for Automated Driving Tests which is developed in the framework of H2020 ARCADE project. A FOT is defined as a study undertaken to evaluate a function, or functions, under normal operating conditions in road traffic environments typically encountered by the participants using study design so as to identify real-world effects and benefits [7].

Figure 7. Overview of the FESTA methodology [7]

FESTA starts with the description of the functions, and the use cases, and the description of research questions and hypotheses, from which the performance identifiers are derived. The study is then designed, data collection processes, and during the FOT data is collected, which is then used to assess the research questions and hypotheses. The collected data is used for assessment of the socio-economic impacts, such as safety, mobility and environment.

The FESTA methodology has been considered for the design of 5G-Routes testing methodology. However, the FESTA methodology is designed for the evaluation of mature ICT technologies in real traffic environments. Most of the CCAM trials in 5G-ROUTES will be performed in environments, which are closed for other traffic. The main purpose of the 5G-ROUTES evaluation is to identify the impact of 5G on the CCAM use cases, and not on the impact of the 5G-ROUTES use cases on traffic. 5G-ROUTES will use the FESTA approach and the FESTA handbook as reference during the different phases of evaluation.

3.1.5 TRUSTS

The TRUSTS project (Trusted Secure Data Sharing Space), which aims to develop a data-sharing platform for secure, trustworthy and compliant data exchanges to GDPR regulation. Deliverable D2.4 of this project [10], which was edited by 5G-ROUTES partner EBOS, defines the methodology and toolset for a comprehensive and robust analysis of the data marketplace technologies and the vertical use cases that will be implemented within the framework of the TRUSTS Project. The business validation in TRUST is performed by utilizing the “Lean Startup” [16] methodology. Business validation will be implemented throughout business validation templates, functional requirements templates and business questionnaire. The technological validation in TRUSTS is performed by utilizing the “Test-Driven Development” (TDD) methodology via unit tests and/or user acceptance, which is similar to the methodology to be adopted by the 5G-ROUTES project. -In TRUSTS, technological validation and business validation go hand in hand, involving 3 sets of business validation and 2 set of technological validations, allowing interaction between the business needs, business models and technological enablers:

- 1st Business Validation: allowing the validation of functional requirements and business information
- 1st Technological Validation: validate the technical implementation during a first set of trials, through user acceptance tests.
- 2nd Business Validation, taking the results of the previous phases into account.
- 2nd Technological Validation: validate the performance of the final version of the technical implementation.
- 3rd Business Validation, validation of the final systems via the measurement of KPIs and defining the gap towards commercializing the environment.

3.1.6 Use by 5G-ROUTES testing framework

5G-ROUTES will use aspects of the testing frameworks mentioned in the previous sections.

5G-ROUTES uses the iterative Plan-Do-Check-Act approach, which is also used by the TRUSTS project, and uses a similar cycle for the technological validation. The business validation process in 5G-ROUTES is based on the approach of the 5G-SOLUTIONS project. Also the Tenant Web approach is based on the KPI visualisation tool of 5G-SOLUTIONS.

5G-ROUTES addresses cross-border CCAM, like 5G-MOBIX, and will use similar concepts regarding the technical evaluation. Concepts and guidelines of the FESTA handbook will be used during different phases of the evaluation.

3.2 Testing framework concept

5G-ROUTES applies an iterative approach for development and testing, which is based on Deming's Plan-Do-Check-Act approach. The process [10] :

- a. The specific use case scenario will be tested and technically validated in several iterations, continuously refining the technological implementation of the scenario.
- b. It is also a mutual consideration that it is better to test as much as possible in early phases, in order to avoid investments which are not addressing to a user's need in the market.
- c. A clear understanding of the stakeholders' needs and what is valuable and viable for the data marketplace.
- d. To understand that the problem or addressed need is clearly understood at some point of time, and that the iterations are concentrating on the technical adaptation and validation

The 5G-ROUTES roadmap follows the **3GPP standardisation releases R.16 and R.17**. This is achieved through three iterative and consecutive testing cycles each lasting for 6 months (i.e. October 2021-March 2022, May 2022-October 2022 and December 2022-May 2023), preceded by relevant setup/preparation and lab trial periods and followed by corresponding parallel evaluation and/or re-design/upgrade improvements periods to ensure a smooth and aligned evolution of the validations in the field trials.

The performance KPIs of each use case will be evaluated during the different testing cycles, to illustrate how 5G capabilities and 5G-Routes technical enablers are leveraged and how they impact application performance. 5G-ROUTES use-cases will showcase a wide gamut of CCAM services, each with a unique set of network-related and application-related KPIs. The impact of 5G technologies (both R16 and R17) and 5G-Routes technical enablers on the aforementioned KPIs will be measured and quantified. A special emphasis will be placed on service continuity, i.e., how the application performance is impacted during handovers between 5G telecom operators or between Cellular and Satellite connectivity. Multiple cross-border scenarios will be tested in field trials, involving multimodal modes of transport (i.e., automotive, rail and maritime). Moreover, systematic feedback loops will be established, for continuous refinement through data collection and data analysis. Conclusions and recommendations will be drawn including recommendations for further trial validations. When possible, the impact of 5G deployment will be also analysed so to potentially allow operators to evaluate their 5G network deployment scope, pattern and duration.

The nature of the use cases, i.e. cross-border CCAM including automated driving, poses additional challenges to the testing.

Cross-border 5G scenarios involve networks of two different MNOs. Border crossings and are not located near the research and development facilities, hence on-site testing involves travelling of both research personnel and the equipment, such as the research vehicle prototypes.

For the trials of the automated driving use cases, prototype vehicles are used, and both access to the vehicles as well as testing facilities are restricted. For these reasons, testing of the use cases will be performed at facilities, to which the researchers have easy access, and then validated at the cross-border sites.

Another issue is the frequency of border crossings, especially for maritime (and rail) traffic. For road crossings, vehicles can be driven over a cross-border route, which crosses the border multiple times within a short period of time. Ferries, however, have a fixed timetable and cross border only a few times a day (e.g. Eckerö Finbo crosses the border 4-6 times per day).

A major challenge with the testing of automated driving are the permits needed for operation of the vehicle on public roads in both Estonia and Latvia, as well as the permit of the local authorities to use the road. In addition, testing of some of the CCAM use cases require, for safety reasons, the road is closed for other traffic. However, as the A264 is a two-way road without central barrier with a single lane per direction, and one of the most important roads linking Estonia and Latvia, permissions from the road authority to close the road for automated driving testing, are extremely unlikely. Negotiations have to be performed with national and local authorities to select a suitable road for testing, and which can be covered by the 5G networks.

For these reasons there are two types of tests in 5G-ROUTES:

- Technical testing in **lab trials**. The purpose of the lab trials is to test the functionalities and the readiness of the use cases in restricted closed areas, and allow the fine-tuning of the 5G technological enablers which will be integrated in the large-scale trials, so as to address most of the challenges, minimize the risks and reduce the uncertainties before the large-scale field trials are set and executed.
- **Field trials** will validate the capabilities of both the 5G technology and the use cases of the vertical industries (i.e. automotive, infotainment, transport/logistics) so as to enable their commercial exploitation. During the project, each use case will deploy a layered testing practice to drive development, involving significant industry representative tests, verifications and validations. **Two types of large-scale trials** will be conducted:
 - o **Localized large-scale trials** aiming at **localized validation of 5G** enabling technologies' features and capabilities in the cross-border areas (i.e. Valga, Tallinn -Helsinki ferry).
 - o **Wider larger scale trials**, validating 5G enabling technologies' features and capabilities in **significant portions of motorways, railways and shipways** along the corridor Valga-Tallinn-Helsinki.

The phases of the Deming's Plan-Do-Check-Act are mapped in 5G-ROUTES as:

- Plan: design of the use case. During this phase both the use case is defined, and the test cases are defined.
- Do: development and testing in lab trials. The use case functionalities are developed and tested in laboratory conditions. In parallel the infrastructure and the required network functionalities are deployed at the trial sites. The evaluation plan for the trial phase is elaborated. The data collection and evaluation tools are validated.
- Check: trial execution and data collection in the trials.
- Act: evaluation and formulation of improvements. Based on both the technical performance and business validation results, suggestions for improvements are derived and - within the limits of available time and resources - implemented in the next cycle.

Figure 8. Iterative test cycle in 5G-ROUTES

3.3 Technical performance assessment framework concept

The evaluation data for the KPIs will be collected at local sites and the large-scale tests, and potentially at the lab trials, dependent on the nature of the application, the availability of resources (network functionalities, vehicles, infrastructure sensors). The baseline for the evaluation current commercial network configurations, i.e. 4G. The impact of 3GPP R16 and R17 on the use cases will be evaluated.

The data for the evaluation is collected from the different components, and then fed into the Tenant Web portal. In order to perform this efficiently, a common format for data uploading will be defined.

3.3.1 General test process

The process for technical performance testing consists of the follow phases:

- The KPIs are further elaborated in D1.1, and the way they are measured elaborated in D1.3. A common format for data collection will be specified and reported in an internal report by March 2021.
- During use case development, each use case will integrate logging of the data. Tools will be made available for uploading of the data to the Tenant Web, where the information will be visualised. The processes for data collection will be set up.
- During the lab tests, the use case components will be verified. The pilot readiness will be verified at the end of the lab trial phase, through assessment that all the equipment, data communications and logging, software and algorithms are working as planned. The results of the lab trial findings will be reported by September 2021.
 - o During the lab trials, reference data can be collected, dependent on the availability of all equipment and the lab trial sites.
 - o During the lab trial sites, the pilot readiness will be verified as far as possible. Remote verification techniques will be used to check the interfaces between the different components and the access to the networks at the large-scale trial sites.
 - o D3.8 deliverable on the initial lab trials and field trials operational readiness in September 2021.
- The first localized large-scale trial cycle (R16) will take from October 2021 to March 2022. During the trials' evaluation data will be collected and KPIs calculated.
- The evaluation results of the first trial phase will be reported in D4.6 by April 2022.
- The second run of lab trials will take place in the first half of 2022. During these lab trials the use case functionalities will be refined and potentially redesigned or updated, based on the results of the evaluation, and taking into account R17 functionalities. The second run of lab trials will be reported in D3.9 in July 2022.
- The experiences during the first lab trials run and the localized large-scale trial will be used to produce a new version of the test assessment report by August 2022.
- The Second localized large-scale trial cycle with 3GPP Release 17, is planned from May 2022 until October 2022. During this period, a set of test runs, similar to the first trial cycle will be performed to check for the impact of R17 on the functionalities. The results of the second localized large-scale trials will be reported in D4.4 by October 2022.
- The second run of large-scale trials will be evaluated, and the results reported in the second evaluation report D4.7 by November 2022.
- A final set of lab trials will take place until February 2023. During these lab trials the use case functionalities will be refined and potentially redesigned or updated, based on the evaluation results of the second trial cycle. The results will be reported in the final report on lab trials by February 2023.
- The final versions of the use case scenarios will then be executed in the extended large-scale trials (R17). The trials will be reported in D4.5 by May 2023.
- The results, which were collected, during the large scale trials, will be collected and evaluated, and reported in the report D4.8 "Final evaluation report and lessons learned" by May 2023.

Baseline and impact of configurations

The main aim of the performance is to test the impact of Release 16 and Release 17 functionalities on the CCAM use cases. Technical performance evaluations measure the improvement of new technology and tools compared to a baseline situation. For 5G-routes, the planned baseline is the current commercial network configurations, i.e. 4G. Baseline measurements may however not always be possible:

- 5G may enable use cases which are not possible to be performed with 4G.
- Deployment of the measurement tools may not be possible: in the project, the measurement of KPIs is incorporated in the design of the use cases, and they cannot be integrated in products which are already in operation.

During technical performance evaluation, different configurations of the network may be tested, and the impact of technological choices on the performance of the use cases be monitored. This can include e.g.:

- Standalone vs Non-Standalone network
- Use of Mobile Edge Computing for shortening the transmission path or for local processing
- Use of Slicing.

Test logistics

The duration of the large-scale trials consists of three periods of 6 months. The performance of the tests may pose several logistic issues, such as:

- Trial demonstrations may involve expensive equipment which have to be brought on site by the project partners, such as instrumented vehicles, and broadcast equipment, requiring time and resources for travel to the trial site.
- The test area has to be closed to other traffic in order to demonstrated automated vehicle use cases. First discussions on this issue with the local authorities have been performed, and the test authorities are positive towards the tests.

For both reasons, trials of the use cases will be concentrated in specific test sessions tests are limited in time. The closure of the road has to be agreed with the local authorities. Dependent on the received permits, the trials of the automated driving use cases will be concentrated in test sessions with a duration of 1 day to 1 week.

Several CCAM use cases make use of the same vehicles, and hence will be tested during the same test period. This makes logistics even more challenging, as the available testing time has to be distributed over several use cases.

3.3.2 Lab trial locations

3.3.2.1 CTTC 5G Testbed Barcelona

A 5G testbed based on OpenAirInterface 5G and ETSI Open Source MANO stack will be provided by CTTC, which leverages a Cloud Radio Access Network (C-RAN) architecture, with a 5G core and a fully virtualised 5G RAN and an optical/wireless Fronthaul. Figure 9 gives a high-level view of the 5G testbed.

Figure 9. CTTC 5G Testbed

5G network configuration and relevance for 5G-ROUTES

Whitebox servers are used to implement all RAN functionalities, i.e. the 5G gNB, Remote Radio Head (RRH), and BaseBand Unit (BBU) with the OAI 5G software stack. Moreover, the 5G testbed supports an optical/wireless Fronthaul based on 10 GigE optical and mmWave links, allowing the 5G RAN functions to be split between the BBU and the RRHs. The RRH units are implemented with Small Form Factor PCs that are connected to a USRP X310, which implements the RF functions. Alternatively, 5G gNBs are connected directly to the 5G EPC via 10 GigE optical backhaul connections. The 5G testbed supports all traffic types, including eMBB and URLLC for high bandwidth / low latency applications, as well as mMTC traffic from NB-IoT and LoRA sensors and actuators. The 5G testbed converges the OpenDaylight SDN controller and the FlexRAN wireless SDN controller to provide dynamic end-to-end slicing support.

Use case testing at CTTC

The following use cases will be tested in Barcelona:

- **UC1.1 Dynamic vehicles platooning.** The scenario will be simulated in the CARLA simulator and the impact of 5G on the scenario tested in the CTTC environment.
- **UC1.2 Cooperative lane change.** The scenario will be simulated in the CARLA simulator and the impact of 5G on the scenario tested in the CTTC environment.
- **UC4.1 360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go.** The tests will be focused on measuring the network latency and how it affects the user QoE.
- **UC4.2 3D real-time virtual collaboration on the go** The tests will be focused on measuring the network latency and how it affects the user QoE.
- **UC5.2 5G-based Proactive and Multimodal Management of Passengers and Freight.** The CTTC 5G testbed will be used for testing prior to the real-life deployment at the via Baltica corridor. The connectivity and functionality of all the use case components (OBU, RSU, smartphones, Cloud/Edge server) will be tested, as well as the proper functionality of the developed resource allocation and risk assessment algorithms. Two UC scenarios are identified of interest and are under investigation to be tested and validated in CTTC Lab in Barcelona. The scenarios are described in more detail in section 6.5.2
 - *Scenario 1:* Multimodal network slice prediction, negotiation and management for passengers and freight when crossing borders
 - *Scenario 2:* Multimodal automated border control for passengers and freight.

3.3.3 TTU 5G Testbeds in Tallinn

5G network configuration and relevance for 5G-ROUTES

5G-IoT testbed: DORM (latformd cOmpact latformd latform) is located at TTU campus and includes 50 end-user enabled devices with NB-IoT modules and sensors, a 5G base station manufactured by Ericsson and commercially operated by TELIA and a cloud platform for data analysis and predictive algorithms. The DORM nodes are deployed across TTU's campus to collect data from their surroundings through dedicated sensors, aggregates the collected data and transmits them to the base station, which subsequently forwards the data to the "Cloud Platform Server", which provides data analytics and predictive algorithms for decision making and data storage.

5G D2D SideLink testbed: Lab trials on V2V and V2I communication will be conducted initially in TTU's 5G sidelink testbed, which comprises of multi-hop D2D communication based on open source OpenAirInterface (OAI) to transmit information in real-time. USRP software-defined radio boards are configured as Ues that are capable to communicate in multi-hop fashion with and without the base station using Proximity Services.

Figure 10. TTU 5G test site facility in Tallinn

Use case testing in Tallinn

The following use cases will be tested in Tallinn:

- **UC2.1 Real-time traffic info and cooperative intersection collision control.** Swarco will provide the necessary information to TTU to perform tests, such as simulations. The other functionalities will be tested in Swarco facilities.
- **UC3.2 Connected maintenance.** Initial testing will be carried out with testing basic connectivity and validating communication in lab environment. CANbus (OBD) interface will be implemented with GPS sensor data to demonstrate reading sensor data and sending data through 5G-IoT base station to cloud server where data will be stored and analysed.

3.3.3.1 VTT 5G Test site in Tampere

VTT's test site is located in Tampere, Finland, which is at the end of the "Via Baltica-North" 5G corridor, where the specific test site enables automated driving sub-system experiments against the commercial network in the 5G corridor.

5G network configuration and relevance for 5G-ROUTES

The test site has 10 base stations which will be upgraded to support 5G functionality, operating at 2.6 GHz band (Figure 11). The test network is operated by Business Tampere and is currently being updated. Eight base stations are located in the district of Hervanta. One of the functions of the test network is support of a robotic minibus, which operates in Tampere in the framework of the H2020 SHOW project. The ninth base station is installed at the Hervanta campus of the University of Tampere, and one base station is installed at a trailer of VTT, which can act as mobile RSU (Road Side Unit). The trailer is also equipped with an Intrinsync C-V2X device, implemented in the 5.9 GHz band. The mobile RSU is equipped with MEC units and data is transmitted via MQTT interface to the

servers for evaluating KPIs offline. The aim of the lab trials at this test site is to benchmark the differences of commercial networks and capacities in different frequency bands over a controlled environment. The test site facility also includes RTK supported GNSS positioning.

Figure 11. Tampere 5G test site

Figure 12. Motorspace test track

CCAM testing facilities

VTT has developed a set of prototype vehicles, which will be used for testing the capacity of infrastructure in the 5G corridor to provide sufficient data to enable automated driving functions testing.

The vehicles have permits for testing of automated driving in Finland, and tests can be performed also on public roads under controlled conditions. The road network in the test area mainly contains of urban roads (two-way roads without central barrier) and as well one road with 2 carriageways and 2 lanes.

Tests, not requiring any vehicle automation functionalities, will be tested in the Hervanta district. In addition, VTT has access to the Motorspace racetrack (Figure 12) near Tampere-Pirkkala airport for testing of safety critical scenarios

Use case testing in Tampere

The following use cases will be validated in lab trials in VTT's 5G test site.

- **UC1.3 See through view for safe automated overtake** The see-through functionality will be tested in the 5G test network on public roads by equipping 2 vehicles with 5G 3GPP R16/R17 equipment. The C-ITS functionalities (i.e. assessment by the vehicle whether overtaking is possible and communication with other vehicles) will also be tested on the same public roads. Due to safety risks, actual overtaking manoeuvre is only planned to be tested on the closed track in Pirkkala. The automated overtaking functionality will be implemented in VTT's prototype research vehicle, the see through functionality will be tested also on EDI's vehicle.
- **UC2.2 Traffic jam chauffeur** The communication between connected vehicles will be tested on public roads in the Tampere test site. The braking functionality will be tested first near VTT's facilities, on the controlled test site and potentially on public roads in the Tampere test site. The steering facility will be tested in the closed test track in Pirkkala, using 3 connected vehicles. The possibility to test the steering functionality on public roads, depends on the possibility to limit the traffic on the two carriage-way road in the test site.
- **UC3.1 Sensor sharing** between connected vehicles will be tested on public roads in the Tampere test site. Two or three prototype vehicles will exchange sensor information with each other over the 5G network, and with the MEC in the network. The prototype vehicles exchanging the information will be provided by VTT (for lab trials), VEDECOM and EDI.

3.3.3.2 Satory

CCAM testing facilities

The trial site is located at Satory, near Paris. It's a closed track site with a multiple type of road infrastructure facilities (urban and semi-rural roads).

It offers more than 3km of road circuit. A speed circuit (90 Kmh) is also available for testing specific automotive use cases.

The circuit is already equipped with a 4G private network (10 MHz of spectrum at 3.6 Ghz). 5G mmWave experimental network (200 MHz at 26GHz) is planned to be ready by the end of 2020.

Figure 13. Satory test track

Use case testing in Satory

The following use case will be tested in Satory: **UC3.3 VRU collision avoidance**

3.3.4 Trial sites

3.3.4.1 Road border crossing between Estonia and Latvia in Valga

The E264 crosses the border between Latvia and Estonia in the twin city of Valga/Valka. Figure 14 shows the border crossing. Please note that the border crossing is close to an intersection. The E264 motorway is a two-way road with one lane in each direction without central barrier. Also the other border crossings between Latvia and Estonia in Ikla and Tsiiruli are on similar two-way roads.

Figure 14. Border crossing between Latvia and Estonia on the E264 (in Google Maps)

For the use case 2.1 trials, an intersection in Valga will be instrumented with traffic lights. The location of the intersection will depend upon negotiations between the relevant partners in the consortium (Swarco, Telia) and the local authorities.

Due to the nature of the border crossing and the road network, some CCAM use cases are not directly relevant at the actual border crossing (Figure 14), such as:

- UC1.2 cooperative lane change since there is only 1 lane in both directions
- UC1.3 automatic overtaking: traffic regulations do not allow to overtake on the border crossing (see Figure 14)
- UC2.2: steering in traffic jam chauffeur, is not possible since only 1 lane in both directions

5G network configuration

The network in Valga/Valka will be developed taking the needs of the project into account, and is described in more detail in D1.3. The initial plan is shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15. Initial plan of the location of 5G base stations at both sides of the border in Valga

Trialing CCAM in Valga

The following use cases will be trialed in Valga:

- **UC2.1 Real-time traffic info and cooperative intersection collision control.** This use case will be demonstrated at a real or virtual intersection in the city of Valga.

- **UC2.2 Traffic jam chauffeur** The communication between connected vehicles will be tested in Valga. The automated functionalities will only be tested on closed roads.
- **UC3.1 Sensor sharing** between connected vehicles will be tested on roads in Valga/Valka. Two or three prototype vehicles will exchange sensor information with each other over the 5G network, and with the MEC in the network. Evaluation data for the communications will be collected during the tests on the public road.
- **UC3.2 Connected maintenance**
- **UC3.3 VRU collision avoidance**

Several use cases involve automated control of the vehicle (UC1.1, UC1.2, UC1.3, UC2.2, UC3.3). Part of the functionalities of these use cases, e.g. the see-through functionality of UC1.3 could be tested in Valga, and communication between vehicles in UC2.2.

For assuring the safety of all road participants, the road should be closed for other traffic during testing of these use cases. For testing these use cases, the following conditions need to be fulfilled:

- The road must be suitable for testing of the use cases (e.g. required amount number of lanes)
- The area should be covered by the 5G communication infrastructure.
- The road authorities provide the permission to close the road.

The consortium is assessing different alternatives. A suitable road for testing in the neighbourhood of the border crossing is e.g. the national road 6 at the northern edge of the city of Valga, which follows the Estonian-Latvian border for several kilometres (Figure 16). An alternative is road 67, following the Estonian-Latvian border for several kilometres at the eastern edge of the city of Valga. The possibility to use one of these locations is further examined, but it depends on the possibilities of the network operators to cover this stretch with the 5G base stations. The selection of the location for testing will be described in D1.3 and D1.5.

Figure 16. Estonian national road 6, at the north of Valga following the Estonian-Latvia border. The border is on the left soft shoulder of the road (source: Google Street View).

3.3.4.2 Riga Bikernieki Racing circuit

In case the automated driving functionalities cannot be tested in Valga, the tests will be performed at the Bikernieki Racing circuit in Riga, where a virtual border will be developed. Both LMT and Telia Estonia will install a 5G-base station at the racing circuit, which will allow to test handover between networks.

The following use cases (UC1, UC2, UC3) are planned to be demonstrated in Riga:

- **UC1.1 Dynamic vehicles platooning.**
- **UC1.2 Cooperative lane change**
- **UC1.3 See through view for safe automated overtake.** The see-through functionality and the C-ITS communications will be tested by equipping 2 vehicles with 5G 3GPP R16/R17 equipment. Evaluation data for the communications will be collected during the tests on the racing circuit.

See through testing could be performed both on the actual crossing and on road 6. Overtaking will only be tested on road 6 during road closure.

- **UC2.2 Traffic jam chauffeur.** The communication between connected vehicles can be tested on public roads, but the automated driving functionalities, especially the steering functionality, can only be tested on closed track.
- **UC3.3 VRU collision avoidance.**

3.3.4.3 Rail border crossing between Estonia and Latvia in Valga

Only trains from PV (Pasažieru Vilciens) on the Riga-Valga cross the Latvian-Estonian border. In Valga, passengers can change trains to continue to Tartu, the second largest city in Estonia.

For the tests of the use cases in the train, the same wagon will be used throughout the test period. If equipment is installed on a train, the same train will be held on the route during the testing period.

Trains from PV make two trips in both directions between Riga and Valga. There is no congested train traffic in Valga, which makes it possible to test multiple handovers between different networks and ERTMS systems by driving trains across the border in a single test session.

5G network configuration

The network in Valga/Valka will be developed taking the needs of the project into account and is described in more detail in D1.3. The initial plan is shown in Figure 15.

Use case testing in Valga

The following use cases will be evaluated on trains in Valga:

- **UC4.1 360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go**
- **UC4.2 3D real-time virtual collaboration on the go**
- **UC5.2 5G-based Proactive and Multimodal Management of Passengers and Freight**
- **UC5.3 FRMCS telemetry operation**

3.3.4.4 Ferry between Tallinn and Helsinki

A mobile 5G station is planned to be installed a ferry of Eckerö Line. Eckerö Line operates two vessels between Helsinki and Tallinn for both passengers and freight: M/S Finlandia, between the Länsisatama port in Helsinki and the A-Terminal in Tallinn, and M/S Finbo Cargo, between Vuosaari port, on the outskirts of Helsinki, and the port of Muuga Harbour near Tallinn. M/S Finbo is mainly targeted towards freight transport but can also carry 300 passengers. The vessel makes daily 2-3 trips between Helsinki and Tallinn in each direction.

Figure 17. Vessel M/s Finbo Cargo from Eckerö Line (eckeroline.fi)

5G network configuration

In Muuga Harbour there is an existing mobile network base station on top of the highest building in the port area. It is possible to install 5G base station also there. Either 3.1GHz or 700MHz frequency band will be used. For the mobile backhaul fibre optical connection will be used.

On the ferry a 5G base station is planned backhauled by satellite service.

In Helsinki existing Telia Finland's 5G network is planned to be used.

Use case testing on the ferry

The following use cases will be evaluated on the ferry:

- **UC5.1 Goods tracking visibility in multimodal cross-border logistics**
- **UC5.2 5G-based Proactive and Multimodal Management of Passengers and Freight**

3.3.4.5 Large scale tests

During the large-scale tests, the use cases will be tested over the whole corridor, from Valga over Tallinn to Helsinki.

- **UC1.1 Dynamic vehicles platooning.** The use case will be trialled in Riga and Valga, dependent on the availability of 5G network and of the possibility to close the roads from other traffic.
- **UC1.2 Cooperative lane change.** The use case will be trialled in Riga and Valga, dependent on the availability of 5G network and of the possibility to close the roads from other traffic.
- **UC1.3 See through view for safe automated overtake.** The see-through functionality will be trialled between Valga and Tallinn/Helsinki, potentially up to Tampere, by 2 vehicles following each other. Testing is dependent on the availability of the network along the corridor. The safe automated overtake functionality will only be trialled on sites which can be closed for public traffic.
- **UC2.1 Real-time traffic info and cooperative intersection collision control.** The use case will be trialled at selected intersections between Riga, Valga and Tallinn, dependent on the availability of the required infrastructure and 5G connectivity.
- **UC2.2 Traffic jam chauffeur.** The use case will be trialled in Riga and Valga, dependent on the availability of 5G network and of the possibility to close the roads from other traffic.
- **UC3.1 Sensor sharing.** The see-through functionality will be trialled between Valga and Tallinn/Helsinki, potentially up to Tampere, e.g. by 2 vehicles following each other. Testing is dependent on the availability of the network outside the local trial areas.
- **UC3.2 Connected maintenance** The functionality will be trialled along the corridor Valga-Tallinn-Helsinki, dependent on the availability of 5G connectivity.
- **UC3.3 VRU collision avoidance.** The use case will be trialled between Valga and Tallinn/Helsinki.
- **UC4.1 360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go.** The gaming functionality will be trialled on whole corridor Valga-Tallinn-Helsinki (Train + Ferry), e.g. a user playing a collaborative augmented reality game throughout the whole corridor, locating and interact with virtual elements that are placed in the real space and move around them. Testing is dependent on the availability of the network outside the local trial areas.
- **UC4.2 3D real-time virtual collaboration on the go** The VR conferencing functionality will be trialled between the whole corridor Valga-Tallinn-Helsinki (Train + Ferry), e.g. a business person immerse in a virtual multiuser conference, making questions and manipulating a virtual mock up throughout the whole corridor and while changing from the train to the ferry. Testing is dependent on the availability of the network outside the local trial areas.
- **UC5.1 Goods tracking visibility in multimodal cross-border logistics** The functionality will be trialled along the corridor Valga-Tallinn-Helsinki, dependent on the availability of 5G connectivity.

- **UC5.2 5G-based Proactive and Multimodal Management of Passengers and Freight** The functionality will be trialled in main terminals along the corridor, which are covered by the 5G network
- **UC5.3 FRMCS telemetry operation.** The tests will be performed in Valga-Valka region.

3.3.5 Test vehicles

For the CCAM use cases, prototype vehicles will be used. In order to be able to test automated driving in Latvia, Estonia and Finland, the vehicles have to fulfil the requirements of the different countries.

The following research prototypes will be provided by EDI, VEDECOM, LMT and VTT.

3.3.5.1 EDI research prototype vehicle

EDI research platform is based on 2018 Kia soul Electric vehicle equipped with various of perception sensors. It includes following sensors:

- 12 GSML Sekonix cameras for 360 surrounding view.
 - 4 Sekonix cameras with 120FOV
 - 8 Sekonix cameras with 60FOV
- 5 Continental ARS-408 Radars giving in total 180FOV and maximum range of 200m
- Velodyne HDL32-L LIDAR for 360 perception point cloud

Figure 18. EDI research vehicle

There is possible to mount optional sensors and equipment such as:

- Inertial Module Unit Xsens Mti 300-series
- GPS RTK Emlid Reach M+
- COHDA Wireless MK5 OBU kit
- GPS RTK OXTS RT3000

The vehicle is also equipped with DriveByWire (DbW) system what allow to control all necessary actuators such as throttle, brake and steering. The DbW unit is controllable trough CAN 2.0 500kbps interface, additionally utilizing UPD packet base protocol trough Ethernet.

Figure 19. Drive By Wire system used in the EDI vehicle

The entire platform with sensor is connected to the High-Performance Computing Unit – Nvidia Drive PX2, what has 2 Tegra SOCs with build in GPU as well 2 discrete GPUs, thus allowing to enable DNN capabilities including object classification and scene semantic segmentation.

EDI research vehicle will be utilized for the Use cases UC1.1 – UC3.2, for the most of the use cases the vehicle will be used for validating requirements, EDI will provide integration interface for those use cases to the partners leading these uses cases, with necessary refinements if required. While leading UC1.1, UC1.2 and UC2.2 EDI will directly involve vehicle in these scenarios, by executing scenarios at cross border area or emulated environment at test site (D1.1 describes possible options).

The vehicle will be equipped with additional machine vision platform. This will be done in order to unify the setup of other vehicles. Currently it is considered to integrate Mobileye development platform based on EyeQ2 vision processor in order to fulfil Use Case requirements.

Figure 20. MobilEye development platform, which is planned to be integrated in the EDI vehicle

Additionally, vehicle will be equipped with UE (User Equipment) to enable connectivity with appropriate interface to validate the 5G-ROUTES KPIs. The chosen hardware will be potentially for the vendors such as Commsignia, Ficosa, Unex, Kapsch or CohdaWireless.

3.3.5.2 VEDECOM vehicle

VEDECOM will use two prototypes of automated vehicles for 5G-MOBIX:

- 1 automated Renault ZOE called VEDECOM2
- 1 Renault Scenic (perception and communication lab),

Figure 21. Overview of French test vehicles

Renault Zoe vehicle

VEDECOM2 is a prototype of automated vehicle built from a Renault ZOE platform **that will be used only on the Satory test site**. This vehicle has two driving modes:

- Standard manual driving
- Level 4 self-driving mode prototype

In manual driving mode, the performances of the vehicle remain the same as the original ZOE. In self-driving mode, the vehicle integrates several technologies to ensure level 4 automation, as depicted by the following table.

Table 2. Sensors and HW platform overview of Renault Zoe vehicle

Type of Sensor	Units	Model	Characteristics
Radar	1	• ARS 408	• 0.20 ...250 m far range,
Lidar	5	• Velodyne	• 360° perception
Camera	2	• Stereo camera	• Front and back cameras
GNSS	1	• Geoflex	• RTK GPS receiver
Fusion	1	• IBEO	• Fusion box
Communication	1	• YogoKu	• OBU ITS-G5
Ethernet switch	1		
PC	3	• 1 Nexcom • 1 Nexcom • 1 dSPACE	• PC Camera • Perception PC

Automated Driving functions

In order to demonstrate L4 functionalities of automated driving, VEDECOM2 prototype has perception, localisation and supervision functions integrated into the following sub-systems:

The acquisition system:

This system uses onboard sensors for perception and localization functions like SLAM (Simultaneous Localization And Mapping).

High-level systems for planning and supervision: This system integrates lateral and longitudinal control. Longitudinal control is set according to the itinerary and the vehicle's location combined with collision avoidance functionality.

Lateral control follows a pre-determined path established using SLAM or RTK-GPS waypoints.

Vehicle platform:

This system is based on robotic functionalities and aims to control the actuators of the vehicle. It also includes low layers safety.

HMI:

The user can activate or turn off the automated driving mode through the HMI installed in the dashboard of the vehicle. The HMI is also able to display the system information to the user.

Connectivity:

Currently, both vehicles are equipped with ITS-G5 and 4G technologies. We are integrating 5G NR devices as OBU inside the vehicle. The 5G chipset will enhance the communication capacities of the two vehicles by introducing its capabilities to handle higher throughput and lower delays.

Scenic Perception and communication lab vehicle

Figure 22. Scenic Perception and communication lab vehicle

Overall description

The second vehicle used by VEDECOM during 5G-MOBIX is based on a Renault Twizy. Thanks to VEDECOM’s collaboration with Renault, the Twizy has been transformed in an open robotic platform (with an open access to the CAN bus of the vehicle). On top of that, the VFLEX is equipped with different sensors as described in Table 3.

Table 3. Sensors and HW platform overview of VFLEX vehicle

Type of Sensor	Units	Model	Characteristics
Radar	1	• CONTINENTAL	• ARS 308
Camera	1	• Mobileye	• Lane and obstacle detection
GNSS	1		• RTK GPS receiver
Inertial	1	• SBG + atlans	

Perception facilities functionalities:

To acquire data on the test track, we used VEDECOM's perception vehicle.

Advanced Driver-Assistance Systems (ADAS) mostly use cameras to detect lane markers, like the Mobileye system or the Tesla one. That is why we also chose to equip the vehicle with a camera. We opted for a Blackfly 23S6C-C (FLIR), hereinafter referred to as Blackfly, as it has a short exposure time to limit the motion blur, a high image resolution (1920x1200) and a gain that can be dynamically calibrated depending on the outdoor conditions. We configured the camera to take images of 1920x700 pixels because we are only interested in what is below the horizon thus limiting the need for a large vertical resolution.

In order to automatically extract, recognize and evaluate each lane marker, we first create a high-definition map containing the precise position of all the lane markers on the test track with their corresponding identifier. This is used to identify a detected lane marker in a dataset, associate it to its product reference and automatically compute relevant statistics per product. As the vehicle is needed to map and exploit the map, we need to precisely locate it on the test track. The accurate positioning is provided by a system composed of three sensors: an odometer, an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU), and a Real Time Kinematic GPS (RTK GPS). The information from the IMU, the RTK GPS and the odometer are fused to obtain a precise global localization of the vehicle (~5 cm).

Lane detection systems can be affected by obstacles in the image. For example, reflections can look like pavement markers depending on the situation. Range sensors are usually used to resolve this issue. Our vehicle is thus equipped with a LiDAR belt to detect obstacles that are above the plane of the road. To remove obstacles from the images, we synchronized the LiDAR belt with the camera at 12.5 Hz.

3.3.5.3 LMT vehicle

LMT will provide contribution in 8 Use Cases by taking part in CCAM testing, cross-border Latvia – Estonia trials and validation of the Use Cases together with RTD partner EDI (Institute of Electronics and Computer Science of Latvia) from Latvia.

LMT will provide the fleet with 2 electrical vehicles: KIA Soul EV and BMW I3, which will be equipped with radars, cameras, sensors and DriveByWire equipment according to the requirements (e.g. KPIs) and needs by each Use Case: UC1.1; UC1.2; UC1.3; UC2.1; UC2.2; UC3.1; UC3.2; UC3.3. KIA Soul EV and BMW I3 electrical cars are chosen in order to ensure swift integration and task uptake with existing fleet of two EDI vehicles (KIA Soul EV) within the required CCAM ecosystem: cross-car-OEM, V2V, V2N, V2I, V2D, V2P. EU and non-EU vendor vehicles are carefully selected as it's a very important for field trials of novel solutions in real-time connectivity, big data and command and control execution of multi-brand CCAM vehicle collaboration scenarios.

Figure 20. LMT KIA Soul EV vehicle

The multi-brand electronic vehicles (KIA Soul EV/BMW I3) are required for validation of the capabilities of 5G network technology, research on the various details, data formats and capabilities of data from car systems and in-built sensors, evaluate KPIs of the Use Cases indicated before and prioritise the Use Cases depending on the potential for commercialization and Business potential of each Use Case.

During localized large-scale trials at cross-border of Latvia-Estonia (Valka – Valga) and “Bikernieki” race track in Riga, 5G enabling network infrastructure and technologies (5G nodes, 5G NR, 5G RAN, new radio frequency bands etc.) will be validated according to the requirements and defined KPIs for particular Use Cases.

3.3.5.4 VTT vehicle

VTT has a set of research prototype vehicles, which will be mainly used in 5G-ROUTES for the lab trials. VTT’s research vehicle fleet includes the following vehicles:

- “Marilyn 2.0”: Citroen C4 which has been upgraded for automated driving, through computer-controlled actuators. The vehicles are equipped with a set of environmental sensors, and advanced communication equipment.
- “Martti”: Volkswagen Touareg (Figure 23), which has been upgraded for automated driving, through computer controlled actuators. The vehicles are equipped with a set of environmental sensors including Intrinsync module for C-V2X and 5G modem for Uu connections.
- “eLvira”: Volkswagen eGolf, which has been upgraded for automated driving, through computer-controlled actuators. The vehicles are equipped with a set of environmental sensors.

The research vehicles are equipped with a set of environmental perception sensors, such as radar and laser scanners. The vehicle architecture is based on DDS (Data Distribution Service), through which the data of the sensors and the information received through 5G is made available to the other vehicle modules, such as trajectory planning and actuator activation.

Figure 23. VTT research prototype vehicle Martti

The vehicles have test permits for automated driving in Finland and will be mainly used for the lab trial tests in use cases 1.3, 2.2 and 3.1.

3.3.5.5 Other vehicles

For UC3.2 (Connected maintenance) existing vehicles will be used, which will be fitted with OBD readers.

For UC5.1 (Goods tracking) drivers from an LSP will drive equipped vehicles.

3.3.6 Use case specific overview

The following table gives an overview of the tests for the different use cases, giving a brief summary of the vehicles which have to be brought to the trial site, the location of the lab trials, the nature of the trial, and the location of trials. The use cases are for testing divided in two categories:

- Tests to be performed in specific test sessions. To this category belong the automated vehicle use cases, and the use cases involving advanced equipment, which has to be operated by dedicated personnel.
- Living Lab tests, in which tests can be performed over a larger period of time. To this category belong the use cases involving vehicles, which are operating in a naturalistic way, and are instrumented with sensors providing continuously data.

Table 4. Overview of testing locations in 5G-ROUTES

UC	UC title	Vehicle Provider	Lab site	Trial nature	Localised trial site	Large scale trial site
Use Case Category 1: Automated Cooperative Driving						
1.1	Dynamic vehicles platooning	EDI	Barcelona	Test session	Valga or Riga Bikernieki	Selected locations along corridor
1.2	Cooperative lane change	EDI	Barcelona	Test session	Valga or Riga Bikernieki	Riga-Valga-Tallinn-Helsinki, which can be closed for public
1.3	See through view for safe automated overtake	VTT (lab trials), EDI, LMT	Tampere	Test session	Valga or Riga Bikernieki	E264 motorway between Estonia and Latvia borders in Valga city. For automated overtaking: selected locations
Use Case Category 2: Awareness Driving						
2.1	Real-time traffic info and cooperative intersection collision control	VEDECOM, EDI, LMT	TTU Tallinn	Test session	Valga	Selected intersections at the corridor Riga-Valga-Tallinn-Helsinki
2.2	Traffic jam chauffeur	EDI, VTT (lab trials)	Tampere	Test session	Valga or Riga Bikernieki	Selected locations along the corridor Riga-Valga-Tallinn-Helsinki, which can be closed for public
Use Case Category 3: Sensing Driving						
3.1	Sensor info sharing	VTT (lab trials), EDI, VEDECOM, LMT	Tampere	Test session	Valga	Road corridor Valga-Tallinn; Helsinki-Tampere
3.2	Connected maintenance	Vehicles with OBD-reader, EDI, LMT	TTU Tallinn	Living lab	Valga	Corridor Valga-Tallinn-Helsinki (Car/Train + Ferry)
3.3	VRU collision avoidance	VEDECOM	Satory	Test session	Valga	Road corridor Valga-Tallinn; Helsinki

UC	UC title	Vehicle Provider	Lab site	Trial nature	Localised trial site	Large scale trial site
Use Case Category 4: Uninterrupted infotainment passenger services on the go						
4.1	360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go		Barcelona	Test session	Rail border crossing between Estonia and Latvia in Valga	Railway route from Estonia to Latvia in Valga. Automotive or Railway until Tallinn port and then continuation via ship to Helsinki port.
4.2	3D real-time virtual collaboration on the go		Barcelona	Test session	Rail border crossing between Estonia and Latvia in Valga	
Use Case Category 5: Multimodal services						
5.1	Goods tracking visibility in multimodal cross-border logistics	LSP trucks	Vedia lab, Tallinn port	Living Lab	ferry Helsinki-Tallinn	Automotive or Railway until Tallinn port and then continuation of journey via ship to Helsinki port
5.2	5G-based Proactive and Multimodal Management of Passengers and Freight		Barcelona		ferry Helsinki-Tallinn	
5.3	FRMCS telemetry operation		Tallinn		Rail border crossing between Estonia and Latvia in Valga	Railway from Estonia ↔ Latvia

3.4 Business evaluation assessment framework

3.4.1 Business Evaluation Goals

The Business validation process in 5G-ROUTES is challenged with engaging and examining the field Trials with a commercial and business lens in order to identify those solutions that are most likely to become commercially viable and can deliver the most immediate quantifiable value to the stakeholders involved in each Use Case. The overall Methodology adopted has many key activities and actions to ultimately arrive at providing practical commercial recommendations to the consortium:

- Create a detailed assessment of broad market opportunities and the evolving technological, financial and social environment surrounding each 5G-ROUTES Use Case
- Undertake an analysis of the services and players, their roles, and relationships within the added value structure in challenging multi-MNO, multi-vendor, cross terrestrial-satellite, cross-border scenarios to specifically examine the value needs/benefit for each stakeholder in each Use Case.
- Perform impact assessments and cost/benefit analyses of dedicated and validated 5G architecture and CCAM to justify commercially the technologies and the deployment investments, whilst addressing the social and environmental impact.
- Consolidate 5G-ROUTES use cases into 3 targeted cluster groups of applications (i.e. Automotive, Infotainment services and Multimodal transport & logistics services) that can be delivered to the market as bundled commercial services.
- Assign each commercial service with a lead commercialisation partner around whom the business development plan that is created within 5G-ROUTES can be centred.
- To identify and protect key commercially differentiating innovation with Patents that allows the output from 5G-ROUTES to be competitively differentiated on the global market.
- Expand each commercial service sufficiently to understand key dynamics around revenue, cost, investment etc. for each commercial cluster and ultimately prepare a business plan for potential implementation post project completion

The ultimate goal for **the business validation process** is to create anticipatory business plans for 3 targeted cluster groups of applications (i.e. Automotive, Infotainment services and Multimodal transport & logistics services). The knowledge gained to support those business initiatives is strongly grounded in the Use Cases that are examined within 5G-ROUTES and hence we have chosen a Lean Start-up Methodology to help guide the Use Cases from initial ideas through to potential business impact and demonstrate how commercial actors supporting the Pilots could move those outputs closer to commercial reality.

3.4.2 Lean Startup Methodology

Turning brilliant research into successful commercial products is a complex task with many failures. Most failures occur because there is a lack of Product/Market [15] fit or to put it simply, the product or solution that is built is not what the customer wants to buy in sufficiently large amounts to sustain a business. This is a particularly big risk in the fledgling 5G verticals market where so much has already been invested and committed to the underlying infrastructure. The urgency of bringing new solutions to market that can deliver financial returns raises the risk that solution providers may rush towards creating solutions for a problem that does not exist in sufficient scale, or can be more cost effectively solved with alternative solutions. To help avoid this, many early ventures in new markets use a Lean Start-up Methodology [16] as the preferred method to guide their journey to early viability for innovative, new solutions. The Lean Start-up paradigm envisions a new proposition being created based on a new product or service that will be embraced by a market of a sufficient size because it solves the customer's urgent problem. Lean startup is a methodology aiming to develop businesses and products that

are commercially viable in addition to compressing the development time required to move from idea stage to final solution deployment. This methodology also favours stepwise experimentation (over an elaboration of overall planning), customer feedback (over intuition), and iterative design (over traditional “big design up front” development). It is a methodology based on “validated learning”, that is, to validate the hypotheses little by little before investing significantly in creating the final product and begin the journey of scaling the business.

A Lean Start-up Methodology creates a bridge from early ideation to large scale scale-up as summarised in Figure 24. Design Thinking is typically focused on finding a “Problem-Solution” fit (i.e. is a proposed solution a viable way of solving a problem), whereas Lean Start-up is more directed towards identifying a “Product-Market” fit. (i.e. will the proposed product appeal to enough people to create a viable commercial opportunity). Finding a potential Product-Market for our various Use Case in 5G-ROUTES in our primary interest area which is why we have chosen Lean Start-up as the core Methodology to guide the business validation process within the project.

Figure 24. Lean Start-up In context of Design Thinking and Agile Execution

3.4.3 Lean Start-up Methodology as embraced in 5G-ROUTES

A Lean Start-up Methodology is the accepted option for creating founder-driven, investor-oriented start-ups, and while not all elements of the methodology can be adopted in a complex EU research project spread over 3 years with a multi-country, multi-functional consortium, there is strong evidence [17] that adopting a similar approach in the research domain can lead a project to better enable: **i)** the commercialisation of better products and services, **ii)** while being faster to the market, and **iii)** with sustainable business models. In a European Research Project context, the consortium is in many ways restricted compared to standalone, individual startups who seek to address specific problems for a narrow customer segment and grow outwards from an initial pilot implementation to long-term viability. EU research projects, by their nature, must take a broader view that encompasses a range of views and expertise to finally arrive at a body of knowledge that can be transformative for the future of EU citizens. **Nonetheless, the challenge remains to keep research focused on the creating solutions that create value for real stakeholders.**

Figure 25. Lean Methodology Process in 5G-ROUTES

Therefore, the model adopted within 5G-ROUTES is more a hybrid of Lean-Startup thinking and orientation but mapped onto the timeframe and work packages that are inherent in a European Research project. Figure 25 provides a high-level view of 4 pillars of the methodology and the process involved in moving towards a validated, commercially viable plan for those opportunities that are the most commercially attractive. The specific tasks, methods and tools employed in each phase are summarised in Table 5.

Table 5. Tasks, Methods and Tools in Commercialisation Validation

Commercialisation Validation and Acceleration Methodology

Goal	Create a body of work that provides a realistic roadmap for the commercialisation of outputs from the research project that are customer oriented, validated and supported by commercially motivated consortium partners.			
Phase	Customer Validation	Solution Alignment	Business Model Selection	Growth Trajectory
Key Question	Segment and refine specific customer wants and needs	Define and align potential product(s) to target market	Select most appropriate business model to acquire and retain profitable customers	Articulate a business plan for growth and sustainability
Key Tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Market / Stakeholder Analysis and Segmentation Use Case focused Business Validation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agree product(s) to Commercialise/exploit with commercial leader(s) Define Product and Service Portfolio (incl. Patents) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Examine range of potential models Align business model must directly aligned to commercial leader and early adopters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Roadmaps – Financial, People, Product, Marketing, Sales, funding
Methods and Tools	Questionnaires UC Leader interviews Post UC feedback	Product Definition Workshops Commercial Leader Workshops	Business Model Workshops Business Model Canvas, Value Proposition Canvas, PESTLE / SWOT analysis	Financial Templates Commercial leader Interviews

3.4.4 Business Impact Assessment Methodology

The Business impact assessment of 5G-ROUTES will be based on the analysis of the business models and value propositions through the application of the - adapted to the project needs – **Multi-Actor Multi-Criteria Analysis (MAMCA)** methodology that will result to a broad screening of the business opportunities and their ranking, followed by a **Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA)** that will evaluate in-depth the present value of the benefit streams for the selected business cases. The involvement of the internal and external stakeholders identified preliminary in D1.1 and revisited within WP5 will serve a major role in the process. The preliminary results of this work will be reported in D5.3, while the final outcomes in D5.4.

The business impact indicators will be created during the Step 3 of the MAMCA methodology (see below) that will be fed to the CBA for the in-depth analysis. MAMCA methodology uses as its main tool physical stakeholder workshops (see Section 4.4.4.3) for each identified business ecosystem, in order to weight the business criteria at first and then to rank the value propositions against those criteria.

The MAMCA [18] methodology allows to assess and prioritise a set of alternatives (measures, scenarios, strategies, technological solutions etc.), taking into consideration the opinion of experts as well as the preferences of stakeholders. Apart from resulting in the final prioritisation of the proposed alternatives, the MAMCA methodology allows the understanding of the view of each stakeholder cluster regarding the problem and aims at determining an optimum compromise between the different and usually conflicting stakeholders' interests.

The MAMCA methodology consists of 7 steps (Figure 26).

Figure 26. The MAMCA methodology⁸.

Cost-Benefit Analyses are often used to support decision-making in the context of large scale infrastructure projects where actual measured data can be gathered during a longer period of time and the piloting phase also provides information about various cost categories during the trial. In

For cost-benefit analyses in the project, qualitative and explorative methodology will be used in addition to tangible data, in order to investigate the potential of the 5G technology potential in the CCAM markets. To support the qualitative analysis, a set of additional tools will be used (see Sections 0 and 4.4.4.4) in order to

facilitate the process, encompassing questionnaires, focus groups and interviews. Such data will be also processed to the sensitivity analysis in order to better define social benefits. This viewpoint emphasizes the significance of identifying solutions for interoperability and potential operators for data-driven services.

As a summary, Figure 27 shows the timeline and the different phases of both the business evaluation and the business impact assessment.

Figure 27. Phases and timeline of the business evaluation and the business impact assessment.

4 Data collection

4.1 Data collection process and KPI visualisation

For the technical performance, data will be collected from the different 5G nodes involved in the use cases including network equipment (gNB, MEC...), application servers, vehicles and other UEs.

The Tenant Web tool, which is developed during the 5G-ROUTES project, will be used for visualizing the KPI results. The use of the Tenant Web Portal is considered as an important element to 5G-ROUTES to automate and accelerate the execution of the use cases running in parallel, as well as the analysis, benchmarking and presentation of the technical KPIs from cross-border field trials, whilst being in the field, by using big-data graph analytics and cloud-computing for rapid and automated processing of the vast amount of data obtained from the trials.

The data collection and visualization process is the following:

- During the test sessions, or during the trial period, the different devices, which are connected to the 5G network, data is collected in log files. The data is collected in a uniform format, which is agreed by the partners. The data is either collected for each specific test run, or - for living lab tests - continuously.
- At the end of the test session, the main partner responsible for the use case collects the data from the 5G nodes either physically or through connection over the 5G network at the end of the test session. After the test session, the main partner responsible for the use case verifies the quality of the data collected, and, if needed, the data is aligned to the uniform format. The data is uploaded to the Tenant Web portal, using tools provided by the Tenant Web.
- The KPIs are calculated from the data uploaded by the trial sites by the Tenant Web portal.
- The KPIs are visualized in the Tenant Web portal.

The following tools will be provided for data collection

- **Data Collector Module:** module responsible for collecting the data from UCs (via the 5G nodes), anonymizing them whenever needed and storing the output in an internal database. It provides interfaces the integration with a UC is via secured REST-APIs. An additional option is provided by the Portal might be manual upload of log files that will later be digested by the data collector module.
- **Data Processing Module:** module responsible for performing near real-time processing on the collected data and extracting the valuable information that is persisted to the system's database. Data is homogenized and transformed to predefined KPIs corresponding to field trials of different use case scenarios.

Additionally tools may be provided for the starting and stopping of the logging at the different 5G-nodes synchronously.

4.2 KPIs

The KPIs will be defined in more detail in D1.1 and D1.5. The KPIs presented here are based on an initial discussion and are used to specify the data collection processes. The main purpose of the discussion on these pages is to assess which are the requirements, put by the selected KPIs, on the data collection processes, especially for the technical performance assessment. This document will be updated based on these reports.

Table 6. KPI definition, based on 5G-TOURS D7.1

KPI	Definition	Data to be measured during trials
Network KPIs		
Throughput	Throughput is the amount of information transmitted per unit of time. Throughput is usually measured in bits per second (bit/s or bps).	The data rate as perceived at the network layer between two selected end-points [19]
Data rate	User experienced data rate (bps) is a minimum achievable data rate for a user in real network environment. Peak data rate (bps) is a maximum achievable data rate per user.	Message size (aggregated) and number of messages per unit of time.
Mobility	Mobility(km/h) is a relative speed between receiver and transmitter under certain performance requirement.	UE speed,
Latency	Latency is the time it takes to transfer a first/initial packet in a data burst from one point to another. (TS. 28.552). Control plane latency: the time to move from a battery efficient state to start of continuous data transfer User plane latency Contribution of the radio network to the time from when the source sends a packet to when the destination receives it.	Timestamp of message transmission and receipt at all components. The possibility to measure depends on access to the required timestamp, and the possibility to synchronise the different components. Measurements in 5G-ROUTES will concentrate on user-plane latency.
End-to-end latency	Elapsed time from the moment a data packet is transmitted by the source application to the moment it is received by the destination application instance(s) [19]	Timestamp of message transmission and receipt at the applications
Round Trip Time (RTT)	Time it takes for a data packet to be sent to a destination plus the time it takes for an acknowledgment of that packet to be received back at the origin.	Loop time is an alternative for end-to-end latency if the UE cannot be synchronised. Loop latency is measured as the time between transmission and response at the same UE, and hence requires automated acknowledgement at the other end.
Jitter (ms)	Deviation of true periodicity of a signal, variance in packet delay at the receiving side of a communication link.	
Density	Density is a total number of connected devices per unit area (Total connected devices (human & machines communications) within range of 5G signal divided by the total land (average #devices/Km ²)). It is the ability to support the successful delivery of a message of a certain size within a certain time.	

KPI	Definition	Data to be measured during trials
Reliability	<p>Reliability is the ability of the network to perform assigned tasks in certain operating conditions.</p> <p>The KPI describes how often and how many Transport Layer packets are lost in the connection and arrived delayed between the UE and the N6 interface (5G network) or UE and Server (whole network).</p>	log of transmitted and received messages at the applications
Positioning accuracy	Positioning accuracy refers to the closeness of a measured location to the real location of the device at the time of the measurement.	UE location; measured by comparing the position estimated by the 5G network to the position retrieved from a GNSS [19]
Handover time (Mobility interruption time)	<p>The time duration during which a user terminal cannot exchange user plane packets with any base station (or other user terminal) during transitions. [19]</p> <p>Handover time: Mobility interruption time between neighbouring cells</p>	Measurement shall be primarily contacted on the involved UEs, taking into account their local state with respect to their association to the network [19]
Roaming time	Mobility interruption time between cells from different networks	
Service KPIs		
Coverage	Coverage is a total land area covered by 5G signal divided by total land area.	%of the test area covered
Availability	One minus maximum tolerable packet loss rate at the transport layer for that application	log of transmitted and received messages at the applications
Service interruption time		log of connection at UE
Quality of Experience (QoE)	The overall acceptability of an application or service, as perceived subjectively by the end user (definition from ITU-T).	<p>The QoE measurement depends on the type of service.</p> <p>For audio-visual services the Mean Opinion Score (MOS) will be used. MOS is a widely used indicator for assessing the quality of multimedia signals and can be based either on a subjective basis (MOS-AVQS) or an objective basis (MOS-AVQO). MOS-AVQO represents the MOS score obtained from an algorithmic quality evaluation model, which uses real-time objective metrics that can be obtained from information carried in the audiovisual streams.</p> <p>For information services (e.g. UC 5.1) questionnaires will be used to measure user acceptance, e.g. SUS (System Usability Scale).</p>

KPI	Definition	Data to be measured during trials
Quality of Service	QoS may implies a list of KPIs that need to be fulfilled e.g. RTT latency < 10ms AND Reliability>99.999	
Business KPIs		
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure (infrastructure, vehicles, Hardware/software, etc) required to bring CCAM to wide scale deployment	Stakeholder surveys and interviews centred on commercial solution selected for Automotive, Infotainment and Multimodal T&L
OPEX	Operating Expenses (Human Resources, Insurance, sales, marketing etc.) required for day-to-day operation of a CCAM ecosystem.	Stakeholder surveys and interviews centered on commercial solution selected for Automotive, Infotainment and Multimodal T&L.
WTH/ WTP	Customer willingness-to-have and willingness-to-pay values.	Stakeholder and user evaluation surveys/questionnaires.
B/C ratio	The ratio between discounted economic benefits and costs.	Tangible inputs (costs/benefits), sensitivity analysis (stakeholder level) and qualitative assessment through focus groups, interviews and questionnaires (stakeholder and end-user level)
Deployment time	Time to deployment of the 5G-ROUTES UCs in relation to EC 5G Action Plan [20] and STRIA Roadmap for CAT [21].	Deployment Scenarios: Short (2023), Medium (2030), Long (>2030) ⁹ Relevant trials input: Ecosystem maturity, Technology integration and coverage options (if any) through surveys with UC leaders.
Penetration rate	The assessment of how much a product is being sold relative to the total estimated market for that product, expressed as a percentage.	Penetration rate (PR) (%) = (number of customers ÷ target market) x 100 For 5G-Routes UCs we will need to consider the PR of the 5G equipped vehicle (PRV) and the PR of the 5G infrastructure (PRI). So the rate of usage of 5G technology over CCAM is calculated by: PRV*PRI The input is not expected from the trials but rather from the thorough market study (T5.1). For the business impact assessment and considering the wide spectrum of the 5G-ROUTES UCs a market penetration of 100% will be considered to the calculations.

4.3 Data collection for technical performance assessment

The data collected in the project for technical performance assessment comprises of raw measurements and observations from lab and field trials, logs exposing the state of the experiments.

To safely manage research data in a broader sense, a Data Management Plan (DMP) will be defined, aiming to make such data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). The DMP will contain information related to the types of data the project will generate and collect, the standards that will be used to represent the data during the project and how partners might exploit the data resulting from the project. The DMP will set robust management procedures that will protect personal data collected as a result of project activities, as well as client owned data, from unauthorized use or sharing, also supporting GDPR compliance.

Synchronization of the different data sources is critical, especially for measuring latency which is expected to be in the order of milliseconds.

4.3.1 Data Sources

4.3.1.1 Network related data

In order to measure network KPIs, probes have to be inserted that intercept the network in proper points at the network. This equipment can monitor the data flow continuously, and store the data needed for calculating the KPIs. Research data types will at least include:

- a) Aggregated network data per flow/service slice
 - i. provided to vertical industries, together with the relevant measured KPIs;
 - ii. provided to the orchestration to enable its proper functioning and KPIs matching;
 - iii. network data gathered at the field trials;
 - iv. network data gathered at the interworking interfaces of different site facilities;
- b) Specific flow/service statistics collected for debugging and/or failure management purposes;
- c) Detailed data traces collected for specific purposes;

For the assessment of the network performance, two types of tests will be specified:

- Service-related tests, measuring data when performing the use case scenarios.
- Agnostic tests, for assessing KPIs, which are general for different use cases, such as maximum throughput. During these tests synthetic traffic will be generated (potentially in combination with data from the use cases). KPIs to be measured may include:
 - o Throughput
 - o user plane latency
 - o intra-cell mobility
 - o user plane handover interruption time
 - o roaming user plane handover interruption time
 - o reliability
 - o network capacity

4.3.1.2 Vehicle related data

Road vehicle data will be collected for the CCAM use case scenarios. The following data will be collected from the vehicles: positioning data, speed, sent and received message timing and size.

For the prototype vehicles, which are used in the CCAM use cases, vehicle data is collected directly from the vehicle electronics. For use case 3.2 (Remote maintenance), the data will be collected from OBU-dongles and for use cases 5.1 and 5.2 from OBUs installed in vehicles.

Vehicle data is classified as personal data. Most of the vehicles which are used for the CCAM tests are research vehicles, which are operated by authorized personal, and data are only logged for the purpose of the tests, hence no issues with GDPR.

For UC 3.2 (Remote maintenance) personal vehicles of the test users will be used, and for UC5.1 vehicles from a logistic operator may be used, as well as for UC5.2. GDPR issues will be addressed using informed consent forms, where the drivers of the vehicles will be informed on the service and on their rights.

4.3.1.3 Other equipment data

For technical performance assessment, information will be collected from other 5G-nodes, such as infrastructure and IoT sensors connected to the 5G-network, end user devices (including consumer devices) and application servers.

From other UEs at least the following information is collected: positioning data, speed, sent and received message timing and size.

In case the end user device or the IoT sensor has only limited processing capabilities, not all the desired information may be possible to be logged. Synchronisation using NTP or other technologies may not always be possible.

Data collected by nomadic devices used by test users will be anonymized, and it will be assured that the test user cannot be identified from the data logged on the service.

4.3.1.4 Overview of data collected for the different use cases

Table 7. Overview of devices in 5G-ROUTES where data will be logged

Use Case	Network	Vehicle	other devices	servers
1.1	✓	✓		
1.2	✓	✓		
1.3	✓	✓		
2.1	✓	✓	Traffic light controller, cameras, RSU	ICS
2.2	✓	✓		
3.1	✓	✓		
3.2	✓	OBD-reader	IoT	cloud server
3.3	✓	✓	VRU	RSU
4.1	✓	-	User smart device	Users game server, Real-time game server.
4.2	✓	-	Broadcast virtual set, graphics station	-
5.1	✓	truck OBU (MTT150)		backend
5.2	✓	OBU (tbc)	smartphone, IoT sensors, infrastructure sensors,	cloud server
5.3	✓			backend, train equipment

4.3.2 Data storage formats

Raw measurements, for e.g. network KPIs with related parameters, such as timestamps, etc., are stored in plain text format, such as comma separated values (CSV). The raw measurements are pre-processed at the time of data-collection to remove any personally identifiable information, such as IP address, leaving only anonymous and unique machine identifiers along with other parameters related to computations. Logs that contain the history of the state of various processing elements are also stored in plain text format.

In order to be able to process the data from the different sources in an efficient way, a common data format in which the data will be collected or converted prior to data upload to the Tenant Web portal will be agreed.

The structure of the files and the data will be specified in the following months.

A common approach will be used for the numbering of test scenarios and test runs. Common procedures may be defined for the starting and stopping of test runs. This could exist e.g. of the transmission of an agreed message to all components to initiate and stop logging.

4.3.3 Data Quality requirements

In order to be useful for evaluation, the quality of the data has to be assured. This includes the following aspects:

- Timing synchronization. As the latency KPIs are in the order of 10 ms, the time in the different 5G-nodes has to be synchronised in order to be able to measure latency. A high accuracy is required seen the low latencies desired, hence target should be to have accuracy in the 1 ms range. The following techniques can be used for time synchronisation:
 - GNSS time reference for the 5G nodes. Use of the PPS (Pulse per Second) signal allows for synchronisation with other sensors.
 - NTP (Network Time Protocol) or Chrony. NTP typically provides a precision in the order of a millisecond.
 - PTP (Precision Time Protocol)
- The names of the log files are according the agreed principles, e.g. contain name of the logging station, type of log data, timestamp and test run. The files contain all mandatory variables.
- The data is logged in the agreed format. Data are stored in csv files. The different variables are in the agreed units and the agreed format, e.g. timestamp represented as Unix epoch time, and speeds in km/h.
- The values of the logged data are within the expected range, e.g. GNSS-data are not zero.

4.4 End-user involvement and end-user data

4.4.1 End-user participation in testing

The main purpose of the evaluation in 5G-ROUTES is to assess the impact of 5G on the services. In order to be able to distinct the impact of both R16 and R17 to earlier releases, subjective opinions of test users may not result in reliable results, especially for the cross-border effects. The test setup with consumers is challenging, due to both the large time gap between tests with different releases, the logistic difficulties in organising the tests with preferably the same persons at distant time intervals, while keeping similar (before and after) test conditions.

For tests performed during the lab trial phase, traditional recruitment methods can be used, e.g. using personnel, recruitment through social media or using an external service provider. For tests performed at the cross-border, the recruitment of test users is more challenging, especially for the train and ferry cases, as passengers on board have to be asked to participate and the time needed for the traditional user interaction process (briefing, pre-questionnaire, test, post-questionnaire) may not suit many passengers.

Involvement of test-users in autonomous vehicles is challenging, as there may be ethical/liability requirements which prevent taking passengers on board. QoE is not on the planned KPI list for autonomous functionalities.

Hence, the main focus in user acceptance in 5G-ROUTES will be on objective tests for KPIs, which related to user acceptance. In addition, user acceptance of stakeholders through standard questionnaires.

4.4.2 User acceptance tests

For the Quality of Experience evaluation in UC4, MOS is used as KPI. MOS for audio-visual services can be assessed either through subjective tests with end users (MOS-AVQS) or through objective tests (MOS-AVQO). As MOS-AVQS is, due to the issues mentioned above, extremely difficult to measure reliably for cross-border events, MOS-AVQO will be used.

For **UC3.3** the following tools will be used in user evaluation:

- A **User profile** will be used to acquire a generic view on the users' age, gender, disabilities, socio-economic status, and experience of AV vehicle and functions.
- The **Usability assessment** measures the extent to which a product can be used by specified users to achieve specified goals with effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction in a specified context of use (ISO/IEC 9241-11: 1998 Guidance on Usability). The **System Usability Survey (SUS)** developed by Brooke (1996) [22] will be applied during the user evaluation.

- **User experience** measures whether the system in question meets a particular user's needs in the given context but also takes the whole experience into account, including aspects like pleasure and joy of use. The **User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ)** by Schrepp, Hinderks, and Thomaschewski [23] will be used in this context.
- The **User Trust** assessment aims to measure the users' view on whether the system is behaving with high reliability, consequence and easiness of perception. For the evaluation of user trust, the **Automation Trust Index (SATI)** by Dehn [24] will be applied.
- **User acceptance** can be defined as the demonstrable willingness within a user group to employ an information technology for the tasks it is designed to support [25]. The User acceptance questionnaire measures users' willingness to use the system in question and the level of appreciation after the use. Within 5G-ROUTES a set of questionnaires will be used in order to evaluate the users' acceptance, such as the **Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)** developed by Davis[26], the **Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT)** by Venkatesh et al. [27] as well as an extension of the 5-point Van der Laan Scale [28] on 9 – from original 5 - areas that allows an estimation of technology satisfaction and usefulness.

A selection of these tools, especially the System Usability Survey will be used by other use cases which involve end-users, such as UC5.1.

4.4.3 Technical performance data

The following table indicates how test users are planned to be involved in the process:

Table 8. Involvement of test users in the 5G-ROUTES use cases

Use Case	Nature of test users	Location	Type of interaction (questionnaires, logging device use)
1.1	<i>No plans for tests with consumers</i>		
1.2	<i>No plans for tests with consumers</i>		
1.3	<i>No plans for tests with consumers</i>		
2.1	VRUs, personnel of project partners	Valga	technical evaluation (detection of VRUs)
2.2	<i>No plans for tests with consumers</i>		
3.1	VRUs, personnel of project partners	Tallinn, Valga	technical evaluation
3.2	Drivers of vehicles	Tallinn, Valga	OBD-reader and IoT devices installed in the test user vehicles
3.3	general public	Valga	Questionnaires & technical evaluation
4.1	Personnel of project partners	Train, ferry	Technical evaluation
4.2	Owners of HMDs ¹ in the consortium	Train, ferry	Technical evaluation
5.1	LSP drivers	Ferry, Tallinn-Valga motorway	LSP drivers will drive instrumented vehicles
5.2	Personnel of project partners	Ferry, train, Tallinn-Valga motorway	technical evaluation
5.3	<i>No plans for tests with consumers</i>		

¹ due to COVID situation, HMDs have almost become a device for personal use.

Test users have to fill in informed consent forms. Attention should be placed especially if the use of the device which the test user is logged, and the logs of the device use can be linked to the identity of the user. GDPR issues will be addressed in more detail in the DMP.

4.4.4 Collection of data for business validation

4.4.4.1 Customer Validation Survey and Interviews

The Customer Validation element of a Lean Methodology process focuses primarily on understanding each of the personas involved in each of the “early adaptor” scenarios that are envisaged for a project. For 5G-ROUTES, that requires detailed examination of the key personas in each Use Case and the likely benefit that they expect to gain from eventual large-scale uptake of the proposed scenario.

This data will be gathered primarily from Use Case owners and related stakeholders in a Survey format with further interviews where necessary to clarify specific details. Figure 28 provides a sample of the type of questions and data to be gathered in a survey, but the format may be amended to ensure that this community is only polled once for information that is required for this process and also for other business validation activities (e.g. MAMCA/CBA).

<table border="1" style="width:100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width:50%;"><small>5G ROUTES Use Case Name</small></td> <td style="width:50%;"></td> </tr> <tr> <td><small>UC Contact</small></td> <td></td> </tr> </table> <p style="text-align: center;">Business Context and Problem Definition</p> <p>Background <small>Please provide a textual description of the business process and context surrounding the UC. What is the general context of the UC? (describe situation in which the UC arises; be specific, focus on the Business/commercial side rather than technical)</small></p> <p><small>Under what circumstances does the UC arise?</small></p> <p><small>How often?</small></p> <p><small>Other information?</small></p> <p>Describe the Personas <small>Please describe ALL personas who are directly impacted by the UC</small></p> <p><small>Describe each persona of the 5G Application (Consumer? Org/Business operations? Technology ? etc.); Please be as specific and detailed as possible about exactly what each persona does.</small></p> <p><small>Describe the end user personas (e.g. different types of consumers; citizen; driver;)</small></p> <table border="1" style="width:100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width:50%;"><small>Persona Name</small></td> <td style="width:50%;"><small>Persona Role</small></td> </tr> <tr><td> </td><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td><td> </td></tr> </table> <p><small>Describe the application provider(s) (who builds and supports the applications?)</small></p> <table border="1" style="width:100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width:50%;"><small>Persona Name</small></td> <td style="width:50%;"><small>Persona Role</small></td> </tr> <tr><td> </td><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td><td> </td></tr> </table> <p><small>Describe other actors directly involve/impacted by the UC?</small></p> <table border="1" style="width:100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width:50%;"><small>Persona Name</small></td> <td style="width:50%;"><small>Persona Role</small></td> </tr> <tr><td> </td><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td><td> </td></tr> </table>	<small>5G ROUTES Use Case Name</small>		<small>UC Contact</small>		<small>Persona Name</small>	<small>Persona Role</small>							<small>Persona Name</small>	<small>Persona Role</small>							<small>Persona Name</small>	<small>Persona Role</small>							<p>Describe the Problem <small>Describe in detail the problems that each persona/stakeholder currently experience (AS-IS today before 5G)</small></p> <p><small>Personas (who exactly?) experience this problem (what exactly?) when doing this task (when does it occur?)</small> OR</p> <p><small>Personas (who exactly?) experience this problem (what exactly?) because of this constraint or limitation (when does it occur?)</small></p> <table border="1" style="width:100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width:50%;"><small>End user Persona</small></td> <td style="width:50%;"></td> </tr> <tr> <td><small>Problem</small></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td><small>Task / Constraint</small></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td><small>How is it addressed now? (Pre-5G)</small></td> <td></td> </tr> </table> <table border="1" style="width:100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width:50%;"><small>Application Provider Persona</small></td> <td style="width:50%;"></td> </tr> <tr> <td><small>Problem</small></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td><small>Task / Constraint</small></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td><small>How is it addressed now? (Pre-5G)</small></td> <td></td> </tr> </table> <table border="1" style="width:100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width:50%;"><small>Other Personas</small></td> <td style="width:50%;"></td> </tr> <tr> <td><small>Problem</small></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td><small>Task / Constraint</small></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td><small>How is it addressed now? (Pre-5G)</small></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	<small>End user Persona</small>		<small>Problem</small>		<small>Task / Constraint</small>		<small>How is it addressed now? (Pre-5G)</small>		<small>Application Provider Persona</small>		<small>Problem</small>		<small>Task / Constraint</small>		<small>How is it addressed now? (Pre-5G)</small>		<small>Other Personas</small>		<small>Problem</small>		<small>Task / Constraint</small>		<small>How is it addressed now? (Pre-5G)</small>																																																					
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Figure 28. Sample Customer Validation Survey

4.4.4.2 Focus groups

According to EC [29] “as of 2020, 5G connectivity infrastructure is equally expected to be an important enabler of connected and automated mobility as well as empower innovative digital ecosystems around cars”.

Stakeholder focus group discussions target to establish a first communication for each targeted business 5G-enabled CCAM ecosystem and identify future business-oriented scenarios. The aim of a deployment scenario is to illustrate the future cases (in different timelines), where the 5G-ROUTES deployed use cases, once

implemented, may result to new mobility services. In order to retrieve an overall picture, the discussions of business opportunities, financial models (investments, short- and long-term revenues, subsidies etc.), key stakeholders, partnerships and potential for related new 5G-related services on CCAM will be discussed.

Focus groups can run either before or after the workshops defined below, depending on the timeline of the implementation and deployment of 5G-ROUTES use cases. They are expected to feed, among others, the Step 4 of the MAMCA method.

4.4.4.3 Workshops

Stakeholder workshops will act as a major data collection tool especially for the implementation of the MAMCA methodology. The aim of those workshops is twofold:

- To identify and weight the business criteria
- To rank the value propositions against the weighted criteria and against each other (resulting to max 2 value propositions to be processed in the CBA)

To facilitate the latter, more complex process, stakeholders will be presented with the business context (Use Case or group of Use Cases), including a real (or video) demonstration where feasible, in order to have a better understanding of the business potential. This knowledge will give them the right insight to follow the MAMCA ranking of the proposed value propositions and rate them against the identified business criteria.

One workshop is planned for the business criteria identification and rating (Step 3 of MAMCA method), which will be on a horizontal basis (use-case independent but relevant to the business potential of 5G as enabler of CCAM), and at the next phase, one workshop per each business context that will select the most promising value propositions and the related business criteria where the CBA should focus on (Step 5 of MAMCA method).

A specified goal for the project is to consolidate 5G-ROUTES use cases into 3 targeted cluster groups of applications (i.e. Automotive, Infotainment services and Multimodal transport & logistics services) that can be delivered to the market as bundled commercial services. Each commercial service will have a lead commercialisation partner around whom the business development plan that is created within 5G-ROUTES can be centred. At least one workshop (supported with data collection tools for relevant financial data) will be required with each commercial cluster to gather sufficient data to produce an anticipatory business plans for the commercial actors.

4.4.4.4 Interviews

Interviews will be the last step of the data collection process.

After each stakeholder ecosystem will have been analysed, and the business leaders/ key investors will be identified, the interviews plan to assess the clear business interest in the 5G-ROUTES solutions or otherwise a significant role in an emerging business ecosystem. Such interviews will be restricted to 1-2 identified business investor(s)/ leader(s) per each 5G-ROUTES defined business ecosystem.

The value propositions discussed in the interviews were selected based on a role and interest of an interviewee along with the results of the previous data collection tools. A thorough SWOT analysis will be performed during the interview and corrections to the financial and economic models will be taken into consideration.

Finally, the opportunities for exploitation of 5G-ROUTES business values will be discussed and scaled-up, creating new markets beyond the limits of 5G-ROUTES use cases.

5 Test plan

This chapter discusses test plan issues at a general level. The test plan will be generated before the start of the test session, where information for the evaluation is collected, in WP3 (lab trials) and WP4.

The test plan has to contain:

- description of the test route
- description of the infrastructure, vehicles and other devices used in the test
- description of the test site architecture, including the potential different configurations of the communication network.
- description of the information flow between the different components, including sequence diagram. Description of the messages which are exchanged, including the standards or specification in use. Description of the security messages in place (e.g. TLS, ETSI C-ITS), including details on the PKI
- description of the actors involved in the test.
- description of the test scenario of the use case and the potential variations, with a sequence diagram showing the interaction between the different actors and components.
 - o description in potential network variations to be tested.
 - o determination of the number of test repetitions. Each test run should be repeated 10 times
- in case test users will be involved, setting up recruitment procedures and potential incentives for the test users.
 - o determining the target users in order to achieve statistical significance, and their properties (gender and age distribution, experience...). A minimum of 30 test users is advised.
 - o preparation of user questionnaires and potential translation.
- description of data to be collected and KPIs to be calculated. Specification of the data logging and collection processes.
- identification of legal and ethical issues, such as:
 - o description of the permits needed and the registration procedures for the automated vehicles, both from national governments and of local authorities
 - o privacy related issues. In case test users are included, informed consent forms.
 - o any required ethical permissions, and description how the safety of all participants to the tests is assured
- access to the test route
 - o in case tests are performed with automated vehicles, and tests cannot be performed in free-flowing traffic, description of how access to the test site can be regulated. Information on the permits required for regulating traffic, contact persons, and actors to be involved.
 - o information related to infrastructure on the test site, such as RTK-GPS presence, access to electric power.
- description of logistics issues.
- detailed time planning of the tests
 - o Several CCAM use cases make use of the same vehicles, which have to be brought to the trial sites. Hence, during the same testing period, several use cases will have to work together, and is there need for coordination of the activities, especially if different use cases have different demands regarding the 5G network configuration.

6 Use Case Specific Aspects

6.1 Use Case Category 1: Automated Cooperative Driving

6.1.1 UC1.1 Dynamic vehicles platooning

1. Use Case

Automated vehicles driving together, dynamically form a group, moving at a very close distance from each other at harmonised speeds following a piloting vehicle. All vehicles in the platoon receive periodic data from the leading vehicle, in order to enable their AI-based OBUs to carry on platoon operations based on V2V communications and [LIDAR detection system](#) or environment perception system, thus enabling at least level 3 automation. This information allows the distance between vehicles to become extremely small (less than 5 meters), implying that the gap distance translated to time is in the order of a few tens of milliseconds for vehicles platooning at speeds allowed to drive at the given testing path section in cross-border highways, fulfilling safety requirements. Therefore, the OBU should be able to make calculations and apply them through MEC-enabled RAN stations at ultra-low latencies (i.e. less than 5ms with less than 10% jitter). Only the driver of the leading vehicle remains responsible for steering (level 1 automation), whereas the drivers in the following vehicles are relieved from driving, i.e. from both steering, accelerating, decelerating and maintaining the same distance (level 4 automation).

Figure 29. Illustration of the platooning use case

2. Partners involved and role of partners

EDI – Use case leader. Mainly will be involved as vehicle provider and component integrator for the use case.

LMT – MNO will support with network related aspects e.g. latency/bandwidth measurements in network, MEC capabilities etc. LMT will provide additional vehicle/s for this scenario.

TELIA – MNO will support with network related aspects e.g. latency/bandwidth measurements in network, MEC capabilities etc.

CTTC – Will use 5G testbed at CTTC premises and evaluate scenario with small scaled experimental self-driving cars.

3. Equipment needed for the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors) and providers.

Vehicles equipped with DbW system, perception system (RADAR, LIDAR) for safety fallback procedure, OBUs, GPS RTK, IMU. From network perspective MNOs should provide coverage at test area, as well make it possible to perform “Handover” or/and “Handshake” network scenarios.

4. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g. closed roads, roads with multiple lanes).

Closed road, controlled environment. Non granted persons should not appear at test site during scenario evaluation.

5. Location for lab trials, and high-level description of the tests to be performed at the test sites

The automated driving functionalities will be tested at the Bikernieki race track, in the neighbourhood of the EDI offices.

In addition simulation tests will be performed in CTTC. Simulated data with the CARLA simulator will be tested in the CTTC laboratories as Hardware-in-the-Loop simulation to assess the impact of 5G on the platooning scenarios.

6. Location for large-scale trials (both localized and large-scale)

Riga Racetrack “Bikernieki”. There different racetrack sections were identified for use case potential validation. However, the most appropriate start/finish line:

Figure 30. Potential route for evaluation of the platooning test scenarios in Bikernieki racing track

The possibility to trial the use case on open roads in Valga/Valka regions is assessed, as described in section 3.3.4.1. Possible roads in Valga are roads which follow the Estonian-Latvian border for several kilometres: road 6 at the northern edge of the city and road 67 at the eastern edge.

7. Logging of data: please specify if data of all equipment (from point 3.) will be logged. If not, or if synchronization issues (e.g. with smartphones) are expected, please indicate

RTT – Round Trip Time, distance between vehicles, kinematics parameters (e.g. speed/acceleration/lateral displacement), intercom latency and jitter will be logged by vehicles control system an on-board computer. Necessary statistics will be calculated about other vehicles participation in the platoon.

8. User involvement: please indicate how end users will be involved in the trial, and how information from end users will be collected. Which end users (general public, employees...)?

EDI employees will act as a safety driver for platoon vehicles provided by EDI, possibly more EDI employees will be involved in preparation and scenario evaluation up to 4-5 people.

6.1.2 UC1.2 Cooperative lane change

1. Use Case

As part of the automated driving tasks, a vehicle should be able to apply manoeuvres in an automated manner, e.g. automatically change lanes in highways or at testing ground with required conditions when appropriate, fulfilling safety requirements. For this, the interaction with the surrounding and the cooperation with other vehicles in the vicinity is of absolute importance, especially in the case of blind spots. The relative speed information of nearby vehicles is also considered to determine the risk factor and appreciate the safety of the manoeuvre, to avoid lateral or/and rear collisions with other passing vehicles. All nearby vehicles are informed about the intentions of the vehicle to perform safe lane change and reduce their speeds.

Figure 31. Illustration of the lane change use case

2. Partners involved and role of partners

EDI – Use case leader. Mainly will be involved as vehicle provider and component integrator for the use case.

LMT – MNO will support with network related aspects e.g. latency/bandwidth measurements in network, MEC capabilities etc. LMT will provide additional vehicle/s for this scenario.

TELIA – MNO will support with network related aspects e.g. latency/bandwidth measurements in network, MEC capabilities etc.

CTTC – Will use 5G testbed at CTTC premises and evaluate scenario with small scaled experimental self-driving cars.

3. Equipment needed for the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors) and providers.

Vehicles equipped with DbW system, perception system (RADAR, LIDAR) for safety fall-back procedure, OBUs, GPS RTK, IMU. From network perspective MNOs should provide coverage at test area, as well make it possible to perform “Handover” or/and “Handshake” network scenarios.

4. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g. closed roads, roads with multiple lanes).

Closed road, controlled environment, roads with multiple lanes. Non granted persons should not appear at test site during scenario evaluation.

5. Location for lab trials, and high-level description of the tests to be performed at the test sites

The automated driving functionalities will be tested at the Bikernieki race track, in the neighbourhood of the EDI offices.

In addition simulation tests will be performed in CTTC. Simulated data with the CARLA simulator will be tested in the CTTC laboratories as Hardware-in-the-Loop simulation to assess the impact of 5G on the platooning scenarios.

6. Location for large-scale trials (both localized and large-scale)

Riga Racetrack “Bikernieki”. There different racetrack sections were identified for the evaluation of the use case. However, the most appropriable start/finish line is shown in Figure 30.

The possibility to trial the use case on open roads in Valga/Valka regions is assessed, as described in section 3.3.4.1. Possible roads in Valga are roads which follow the Estonian-Latvian border for several kilometres: road 6 at the northern edge of the city and road 67 at the eastern edge.

7. Logging of data: please specify if data of all equipment (from point 3.) will be logged. If not, or if synchronization issues (e.g. with smartphones) are expected, please indicate

RTT – Round Trip Time, distance between vehicles, kinematics parameters (e.g. speed/acceleration/lateral displacement), intercom latency and jitter will be logged by vehicles control system an on-board computer. Necessary statistics will be calculated about other vehicles participation in the platoon.

8. User involvement: please indicate how end users will be involved in the trial, and how information from end users will be collected. Which end users (general public, employees...)?

EDI employees will act as a safety driver for platoon vehicles provided by EDI, possibly more EDI employees will be involved in preparation and scenario evaluation up to 4-5 people.

6.1.3 UC1.3 See-Through view for safe automated overtake

1. Use Case

The main objective of this use case is to provide enhanced visibility of road awareness for safe automated overtake in order to prevent catastrophic head-on collisions during the manoeuvre. The objective is to support the automated vehicle in overtaking in mixed traffic on two-way roads (such as the E264 in Valga), where the

vehicle's own sensors and the C-ITS messages cannot capture all traffic, through driver acknowledgement with the support of video.

2. Partners involved and role of partners

VTT: vehicle, in-vehicle car environment and testing of automated driving in Finland

ATOS: management of network services for video streaming in the infrastructure

EDI: supply electric vehicles for the validation of the use case

LMT & Telia: network infrastructure

Ericsson: network components

3. Equipment needed for the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors) and providers.

connected vehicle with in-vehicle camera

automated vehicle with HMI for see-through

4. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g. closed roads, roads with multiple lanes).

The see-through view functionality does not put additional requirements on the trial environment, except for 5G environment allowing high throughput and low latency

For the automated overtaking: closed road or test track with at least two lanes (one lane in each direction). To allow overtaking at (normal) highway speeds, with oncoming vehicle visibility, a track of about 2 km would be needed. The required distance for overtaking depends on the absolute and relative speeds of both vehicles. In case a track is not available with desired length, the absolute speed of the autonomous vehicle will be decreased and/or the speed difference to the slower vehicle increased; and the overtaking manoeuvre decoupled from the see through view functionality.

5. Location for lab trials, and high-level description of the tests to be performed at the test sites

Lab trials will be performed in Tampere. See-through functionality testing in Hervanta 5G test network; overtaking functionality in motor test track in Pirkkala.

6. Location for large-scale trials (both localized and large-scale)

The see-through functionality can be tested in Valga and along the corridor

Automated overtaking: dependent on track availability, minimum 200 m (low speed)

7. Logging of data: please specify if data of all equipment (from point 3.) will be logged. If not, or if synchronization issues (e.g. with smartphones) are expected, please indicate

Logging of data at the vehicles: vehicle position and dynamics, communication

Network data

All data synchronized using NTP/chrony/GNSS techniques

8. User involvement: please indicate how end users will be involved in the trial, and how information from end users will be collected. Which end users (general public, employees...)?

No trials with test users planned.

6.2 Use Case Category 2: Awareness Driving

6.2.1 UC2.1 Real-time traffic information and cooperative intersection collision control

1. Use Case

UC 2.1 considers the exchange of information acquired through enhanced real-time traffic visual monitoring which is fed and controlled via V2X communication standards considering 5G network. To do so, the UC 2.1 approach first is intended to collect information of the existing traffic management service to analyse its status and the data acquired at present. Second, with the aim to compare the existing TM systems and the improved C-ITS services in which are integrated the benefit of the 5G network an installation of surveillance camera is performed at the intersection. Third, the real-time video recording help to monitor and control the intersection to evaluate VRU's and vehicles traffic status enabling the analysis of information. Finally, the analysis of the data acquired triggers the actions in terms of the safe passing for VRUs at pedestrian crossing level and the vehicles collision warning boosting the cooperative automated driving.

As a result, UC 2.1 development leverage existing C-ITS services produced by a more coordinated transport networks (e.g., enhancement in terms of vehicle position speed, driving trajectories, collision warnings, user comfort in traffic jams) which simultaneously integrates VRU's novelty services to make them aware about the potential road hazards.

Figure 32. UC – 2.1 Awareness Driving Overall Description

2. Partners involved and role of partners

- Not defined (it is expected to obtain collaboration from local entities and companies)

3. Equipment needed for the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors) and providers.

- 8 Traffic Lights
- Traffic Light Controller
- Cameras (AI enabled)
- RSU

4. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g. closed roads, roads with multiple lanes).

- Urban Intersection

5. Location for lab trials, and high-level description of the tests to be performed at the test sites

At the test site, it is devised to integrate traffic data at intersection level, including radar sensor info of multiple vehicles (i.e. mMTC), including UHD video streams (i.e. eMBB) with very low latencies (i.e. URLLC) and precise dynamic positioning info in real-time, to analyse the data captured by the ICS in real-time to calculate the trajectories of tracked vehicles and VRUs so as to avoid collisions and to minimize false collision warnings.

6. Location for large-scale trials (both localized and large-scale)

E264 motorway between Estonia and Latvia borders in Valga city

7. Logging of data: please specify if data of all equipment (from point 3.) will be logged. If not, or if synchronization issues (e.g. with smartphones) are expected, please indicate

The data of all equipment specified in point 3 will be logged. Issues in terms of communication systems setup could arise.

8. User involvement: please indicate how end users will be involved in the trial, and how information from end users will be collected. Which end users (general public, employees...)?

End users will be considered through UHD video streams and precise dynamic positioning info in real-time for vehicles and VRU's.

6.2.2 UC2.2 Traffic Jam chauffeur

1. Use Case

This use case focuses on highly automated vehicles (up to SAE level 4) that would operate on motorways reaching the cross-border junction, in which a driver is not required for vehicular control. The scenario includes UC vehicles operating in roads shared with other testing vehicles, pedestrians and cyclists or its representation as the dummy targets, all following a designated route towards the border junction. The traffic jam chauffeur application would make automated driving in traffic jams or stop and go conditions more convenient. The application can steer the vehicle and its brakes in an automated way up to a specific speed limit, e.g. up to 70 km/h, monitoring at the same time the speed of the preceding vehicle and its surroundings through several sensor sources (e.g. to detect hidden objects and act accordingly), as well as the trajectories of nearby testing vehicles. The application integrates and makes use both of the lane assist feature of the vehicle to provide an active lane guidance function, as well as the traffic jam chauffeur for automatic braking and acceleration. The

application would therefore enable lateral and longitudinal guidance, relieving also the driver from the responsibility for steering.

Figure 33. Illustration of UC2.2: Traffic Jam Chauffeur

2. Partners involved and role of partners

EDI – Use case leader. Mainly will be involved as vehicle provider and component integrator for the use case.

LMT – MNO will support with network related aspects e.g. latency/bandwidth measurements in network, MEC capabilities etc.

TELIA – MNO will support with network related aspects e.g. latency/bandwidth measurements in network, MEC capabilities etc.

CTTC – Will use 5G testbed at CTTC premises and evaluate scenario with small scaled experimental self-driving cars.

3. Equipment needed for the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors) and providers.

Vehicles equipped with DbW system, perception system (RADAR, LIDAR) for safety fall-back procedure, OBUs, GPS RTK, IMU. From network perspective MNOs should provide coverage at test area, as well make it possible to perform “Handover” or/and “Handshake” network scenarios.

4. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g. closed roads, roads with multiple lanes).

Closed road, controlled environment, roads with multiple lanes, VRUs representation. Non granted persons should not appear at test site during scenario evaluation.

5. Location for lab trials, and high-level description of the tests to be performed at the test sites

Riga Racetrack “Bikernieki” and Tampere.

6. Location for large-scale trials (both localized and large-scale)

Riga Racetrack “Bikernieki” There different racetrack sections were identified for use case potential validation. However, the most appropriate start/finish line is shown in Figure 30.

The possibility to trial the use case on open roads in Valga/Valka regions is assessed, as described in section 3.3.4.1. Possible roads in Valga are roads which follow the Estonian-Latvian border for several kilometres: road 6 at the northern edge of the city and road 67 at the eastern edge.

7. Logging of data: please specify if data of all equipment (from point 3.) will be logged. If not, or if synchronization issues (e.g. with smartphones) are expected, please indicate

RTT – Round Trip Time, distance between vehicles, kinematics parameters (e.g. speed/acceleration/lateral displacement), intercom latency and jitter will be logged by vehicles control system an onboard computer. Necessary statistics will be calculated about other vehicles participation in the platoon.

8. User involvement: please indicate how end users will be involved in the trial, and how information from end users will be collected. Which end users (general public, employees...)?

EDI employees will act as a safety driver for platoon vehicles provided by EDI, possibly more EDI employees will be involved in preparation and scenario evaluation up to 4-5 people.

6.3 Use Case Category 3: Sensing Driving

6.3.1 UC3.1 Sensor info sharing for cooperative situation awareness

1. Use Case

Connected vehicles can enhance the perception of their environment beyond what their own sensors can detect so as to have a more holistic view of the local situation. In this regard, sensor info sharing enables the exchange of raw or processed data gathered through local sensors or live video data among vehicles, Road Site Units (RSU), UEs of pedestrians and V2X application servers, in order to achieve cooperative situation awareness. Vehicle uses its own sensors (e.g., HD camera, LIDAR), and sensor information from other vehicles, to perceive its environment (e.g., come up with 3D model of world around it) and safely performs an automated manoeuvre.

2. Partners involved and role of partners

VTT: vehicle, in-vehicle car sensing and communication equipment and testing of automated driving in Finland

VED & EDI: supply electric vehicles for the validation of the use case

LMT & Telia: network infrastructure

Ericsson: network components

3. Equipment needed for the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors) and providers.

Connected vehicles with V2X capabilities and connection to in-vehicle sensors

4. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g. closed roads, roads with multiple lanes).

The sensor sharing functionality does not pose requirements to the test infrastructure.

5. Location for lab trials, and high-level description of the tests to be performed at the test sites

Lab trials will be performed in Tampere. Sensor sharing testing in Hervanta 5G test network; use for overtaking testing in motor track in Pirkkala.

6. Location for large-scale trials (both localized and large-scale)

The sensor sharing can be tested in Valga and along the corridor

Automated functionality: depends on trial site conditions: as the functionality is not specified, will be made dependent on the test track. Synergy with UC1.3.

7. Logging of data: please specify if data of all equipment (from point 3.) will be logged. If not, or if synchronization issues (e.g. with smartphones) are expected, please indicate

Logging of data at the vehicles: vehicle position and dynamics, communication

Other potential sources providing V2X information will be logged.

All data synchronized using NTP/chrony/GNSS techniques

8. User involvement: please indicate how end users will be involved in the trial, and how information from end users will be collected. Which end users (general public, employees...)?

No trials with test users planned.

No trials with test users planned.

6.3.2 UC3.2 Connected maintenance

1. Use Case

The primary objective of UCC3.2 is to enable real time tracking of connected vehicles status from operation and maintenance point of view. Connected vehicular onboard diagnostics (OBD) system will be used to track vehicular parameters and status. Parameter collection and reporting system will be developed which will be combined into a preventive maintenance framework. This framework will combine OBD parameter collecting, OBD parameter reporting, parameter analysis and parameter prediction algorithms. TTU will create, install and configure controller device for collecting OBD parameters as well as communicating with cloud databases through Telia's network. Predictive maintenance algorithms will be developed in order to predict future behavior of the connected vehicular. The framework will be made open in order to change parameters included in the analysis and prediction. Onboard sensors could also observe and evaluate 5G network KPIs in order to be aware of network connection status.

2. Partners involved and their roles

LEADER: TTU

CONTRIBUTORS: ADS, ENIDE, CERTH, LMT, TELIA, WINGS

3. Equipment needed for the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors) and providers.

IoT modules (TTU will provide) for real time recording or to prepare the required contents to simulate it's streaming in trials.

OBD readers (TTU will provide) to render and stream the virtual set and the presenter to the final user end as two high definition panoramic images.

Cloud server solution (TTU and Telia will provide) for data analytics and data storage.

4. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g. closed roads, roads with multiple lanes).

No specific requirements. The system should work in a network with IoT functionality enabled.

5. Location for lab trials, and high-level description of the type of tests to be performed

TTU – Tallinn Will be tested in TTU 5G-IoT testbed. Initial testing will be carried out with testing basic connectivity and validating communication in lab environment. CAN-bus (OBD) interface will be implemented with GPS sensor data to demonstrate reading sensor data and sending data through 5G-IoT base station to cloud server where data will be stored and analysed.

6. Location for large-scale trials (both localized and large-scale)

Localised:

- Road border crossing between Estonia and Latvia in Valga

Large-scale:

- Whole corridor, Valga-Tallin-Helsinki (Car + Ferry) (provided that 5G infrastructure is available)

7. Logging of data: please specify if data of all equipment (from point 3.) will be logged. If not, or if timing synchronization issues (e.g. with smartphones) are expected, please indicate

- All collected data will have timestamp.
- Timestamp will be attached to the data when collected from a car OBD system, delay in IoT communication will not affect time synchronization.
- It is planned to send only defined set of measured sensor data to the cloud server for analysis.

8. User involvement: please indicate how end users (such as general public, or employees) will be involved in the trials, and how information from end users will be collected.

End users will take the role of participants in the way that they will allow access to their cars in order to install equipment. End users will get data about data analysis.

6.3.3 UC3.3 VRU collision avoidance

1. Use Case

This use case aims at improving the safety of VRUs since their presence can be detected by vehicles, or infrastructure sensors which send the information to several other vehicles which may not be able to see the VRU at some point.

Information provided by roadside sensors with efficient timing and content will improve the vehicle perception and can be seen as additional sensors. The raw data will be treated in vicinity of the road entities, i.e. in the MEC, to be quickly processed and the risk analysis will be shared with vehicles.

VRUs using smart devices, send their data (location, speed, type, etc.) to the cloud server, located in internet. This latter, having a global view of the network (vehicles, bicycles positions, etc.) will carry out a risk analysis operation and notify the concerned VRUs about hazardous situation.

This collaborative perception, i.e. information exchange among road participants, allows to enhance the usual perception capabilities of standalone users (vehicles, VRUs).

2. Partners involved and role of partners

VED, TTU, CERTH, TELIA, LMT, EEE

3. Equipment needed for the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors) and providers.

Vehicle

Smart phone

Lidars/Cameras on the infrastructure

4. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g. closed roads, roads with multiple lanes).

Road with multiple lanes

Connected infrastructure

Perception from the infrastructure

5. Location for lab trials, and high-level description of the tests to be performed at the test sites

Satory

6. Location for large-scale trials (both localized and large-scale)

Valga

7. Logging of data: please specify if data of all equipment (from point 3.) will be logged. If not, or if synchronization issues (e.g. with smartphones) are expected, please indicate

Localisation data (cars and smartphone)

high level perception data from cars and infrastructure

road shape (to be calculated)

Data synchronization using GPS Time

8. User involvement: please indicate how end users will be involved in the trial, and how information from end users will be collected. Which end users (general public, employees...)?

Population: General public

Data gathering: questionnaires

Locations using smartphones during the tests (with their consent)

6.4 Use Case Category 4: Uninterrupted infotainment passenger services on the go

6.4.1 UC4.1 360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go

1. Use Case

The main objectives of the use case are to allow groups of up to 40-50 users to play Augmented Reality (AR) video games while on-route, and to provide a fluid and identical AR scene status to all participants without the need to apply dead reckoning techniques that always lend to unfair game situations for users with higher latency connections.

2. Partners involved and their roles

LEADER:

BRAINSTORM: Provide AR/VR application and lead the use case.

CONTRIBUTORS:

ADS: Network infrastructure

PV: Provide access to the railway networks.

ATOS: Validate the use cases in a cross-border multi-operator orchestration environment.

EVR: Provide access to the railway networks.

LMT: Network infrastructure

TELIA: Network infrastructure

3. Equipment needed for the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors) and providers.

Game Server. Graphic station in charge of receiving all users interaction, calculating the status and all the dynamics of the game and finally updating all remote devices accordingly.

User smart devices. Smart phone or tablet including a camera, will display the game status overlaid on the camera capture, depending on where the player is pointing the device, and the last game update from the game server.

4. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g. closed roads, roads with multiple lanes).

Known routes in case the AR contents are decided to be linked to the real world.

5. Location for lab trials, and high-level description of the type of tests to be performed

CTTC – Barcelona

The tests will be focused on measuring the network latency and how it affects the user QoE.

6. Location for large-scale trials (both localized and large-scale)

Localised:

- Rail border crossing between Estonia and Latvia in Valga

Large-scale:

- Whole corridor, Valga-Tallin-Helsinki (Car/Train + Ferry) (provided that 5G infrastructure is available)

7. Logging of data: please specify if data of all equipment (from point 3.) will be logged. If not, or if timing synchronization issues (e.g. with smartphones) are expected, please indicate

- Time code for each communication.
- Delay
- Size

8. User involvement: please indicate how end users (such as general public, or employees) will be involved in the trials, and how information from end users will be collected.

End users, when present, will take the role of game players. They will use the smartphone to participate in multiplayer games.

6.4.2 UC4.2 3D real-time virtual collaboration on the move

1. Use Case

The main objective of the use case is to allow reduced groups of individuals to participate on remote master class experiences through 5G connection, on-route, and fully immersive through head mounted display devices, and with remote immersive user interaction. The use case will provide the required means for the presenter to be stereoscopically captured and inserted in real or virtual scenarios including immersive graphic elements to improve presentations and to enable presenter and final users to communication over specific graphics related to the explanations.

2. Partners involved and their roles

LEADER:

BRAINSTORM: Provide AR/VR application and lead the use case.

CONTRIBUTORS:

ADS: Network infrastructure

PV: Provide access to the railway networks.

ATOS: Validate the use cases in a cross-border multi-operator orchestration environment.

EVR: Provide access to the railway networks.

LMT: Network infrastructure

TELIA: Network infrastructure

3. Equipment needed for the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors) and providers.

Broadcast Virtual Set equipment for real time recording or to prepare the required contents to simulate it's streaming in trials.

Graphics station to render and stream the virtual set and the presenter to the final user end as two high definition panoramic images.

High end laptop to receive and render the high-resolution streamed images to be viewed in the user HMD.

User **Head Mounted Display** to visualize the final images and to track the user head and wands that will be delivered through the laptop to the remote graphics station.

4. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g. closed roads, roads with multiple lanes).

No specific requirements. The system should work in the exact same way no matter if the user is on the route or sitting in an office.

5. Location for lab trials, and high-level description of the type of tests to be performed

CTTC – Barcelona

6. Location for large-scale trials (both localized and large-scale)

Localised:

- Rail border crossing between Estonia and Latvia in Valga

Large-scale:

- Whole corridor, Valga-Tallin-Helsinki (Car/Train + Ferry) (provided that 5G infrastructure is available)

7. Logging of data: please specify if data of all equipment (from point 3.) will be logged. If not, or if timing synchronization issues (e.g. with smartphones) are expected, please indicate

- Time code for each communication.
- Delay
- Size

8. User involvement: please indicate how end users (such as general public, or employees) will be involved in the trials, and how information from end users will be collected.

End users will take the role of participants in the immersive interactive 3D conference. They will wear the HMD and will interact with virtual objects in the scene.

6.5 Use Case Category 5: Multimodal services

6.5.1 UC5.1 Goods tracking visibility in multimodal cross border logistics

1. Use Case

The use case 5.1 will focus on supply chain transparency in multimodal transportation, which combines road and maritime transportation. The use case consists of two different cases (see Figure 34): in the first case the aim is to enable continuous connection for cargo monitoring IoT systems during the ship trip between Finland and Estonia. Second case will focus on mMTC, and study what opportunities 5G can provide for cargo monitoring and management on logistics nodes such as ports, where in relatively small area density might be high with a lot of active IoT sensors.

Figure 34. Use case 5.1 illustration (source Vediafi)

2. Partners involved and their roles

- Development:
 - o Vediafi: IoT testing and use case lead
 - o Enide: tracking app
- Network:
 - o Ericsson: communication devices on ferry
 - o Telia: network provider for ferry
 - o LMT: network provider for E67 road
 - o Airbus: satellite communication for ferry
- Testing:
 - o TTU: IoT testing on Tallin
 - o VTT: testing framework and field test support, link between logistics and V2X trials
- Stakeholders:
 - o Eckerö Line: Vediafi subcontractor, who provides one ferry as test platform
 - o Brainstorm: link to passenger transport trials
 - o AS Pasazieru Vilciens: link to railway environment
 - o Esti Raudtee As: link to railway environment

3. Equipment needed for the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors) and providers.

- **ferry and communication infrastructure inside ferry**
- **IoT devices attached to the cargo**
- **truck with OBU (MTT150)**
- **RSU (RMU: roadside management unit)**
- **load simulator tool**

4. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g. closed roads, roads with multiple lanes).

The required IoT environment (RMU) has to be in place in the port

5. Location for lab trials, and high-level description of the type of tests to be performed

-Vedia office/lab (Helsinki): system preparation and pre-testing of set-up

6. Location for large-scale trials (both localized and large-scale)

- Ferry trip between Helsinki and Tallinn (ports will be discussed with Eckerö line)
- Port of Tallinn
- E67 road Tallinn to Riga

7. Logging of data: please specify if data of all equipment (from point 3.) will be logged. If not, or if timing synchronization issues (e.g. with smartphones) are expected, please indicate

Data will be collected from the following devices:

- truck OBU (MTT150)
- IoT devices: to be verified
- RMU
- load simulator tool
- network infrastructure

No data will be collected from the ferry.

8. User involvement: please indicate how end users (such as general public, or employees) will be involved in the trials, and how information from end users will be collected.

- Test will be done in collaboration with LSP, who will participate on evaluation process, if possible
- Pre-testing with Vedia own vehicles

6.5.2 UC5.2 5G-based proactive and multimodal management of passengers and freight

1. Use Case

This use case comes in two Phases. The first phase focuses on the cross-border communication and provides mechanisms for notifications on approaching passengers and freight and assignment of necessary resources in the destination network (proactive resource allocation). In order to achieve this, it is important to leverage on heterogeneous inputs from vehicles, transferred goods and people and to propose prediction algorithms for predicting traffic in the destination network and plan accordingly the needed resources. Finally, it is important to include actions for setting-up and configuring the telecommunication network and any potential vertical aspects. Moreover, the multimodality aspect can be tackled in the second phase where unloading of freight from e.g. trucks and loading to ships can take place in addition to passengers' movement. In this phase, there can be automated checking of freight (towards zero-touch), conducting logistics operations and informing authorities.

2. Partners involved and their roles

WINGS: Use case Leader. Developer of slicing and resource (pre)allocation SW & remote inspection and risk assessment SW.

CTTC: Providing the testbed for testing the use case functionality

3. Equipment needed for the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors) and providers.

- **Cloud/Edge server (WINGS):** Main AI/ML intelligence realizing the use case functionality. Application and user interface, aggregating/fusing heterogeneous information from distributes On-board and

Road-side sensors, smartphones, etc. processing and issuing i) directives towards CCAM vehicles, ii) requests for slice and pre-allocation of resources towards neighbouring networks and iii) risk assessment results towards third party interfaces (e.g. customs authority, port authority, etc.).

- **On-Board Unit/OBU* (WINGS):** comprising the “on vehicle intelligence”, aggregating on-board sensor data, transmitting it to cloud/edge server and receiving orders from the cloud/edge server
- **On-Board sensors (WINGS):** Multitude of sensors to assist with traffic information estimation, vehicle status estimation and vehicle risk assessment. These sensors include (but are not limited to) ECU connector to receive vehicle information (speed, revs, temperature, etc.), IP HD camera, GPS, vibration, luminosity, CO₂, proximity, etc.
- **Road-side infrastructure & sensors (WINGS):** A multitude of sensors will be used to collect information on traffic and incoming vehicles. All sensors will be housed in a Road-Side Unit* (RSU) and will directly communicate with the Cloud/Edge server. These sensors include (but are not limited to) IP HD camera, proximity, infra-red sensors, motion sensors, etc.
- **Smartphone(s) (WINGS):** Smartphone(s) will be used in order to track the location of pedestrians in the test area and to interact with them via a user interface. Other potential uses of the smartphone(s) are not precluded (e.g. use of the camera, collection of additional information, video streaming). The location information of the pedestrians will be used as input for traffic estimation and resource pre-allocation.
- **CCAM enabled Vehicles for trialing:** CCAM enabled vehicle where the OBU can be integrated in order for the use case to be tested at the via Baltica corridor.
- **5G connectivity**
 - **Testbed (CTTC):** The CTTC 5G testbed will be used for testing prior to the real-life deployment at the via Baltica corridor. The connectivity and functionality of all the use case components (OBU, RSU, smartphones, Cloud/Edge server) will be tested, as well as the proper functionality of the developed resource allocation and risk assessment algorithms.
 - **Cross-border network:** Two neighbouring 5G networks will be utilized to test the cross-border functionality of the developed functionalities.

* Both the OBU and RSU will be equipped with chipsets enabling communication over 4G, 5G, NB-IoT and WiFi networks, allowing for benchmarking of performance.

4. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g. closed roads, roads with multiple lanes).

- 5G coverage throughout the trial paths
- Presence of MEC/Edge Servers in the trial environment
- 5G testbed and network to enable creation and real time update of network slices
- 5G testbed and network to enable creation and real time update of selected resources across the trial paths.
- Mixed presence of vehicles and pedestrians (e.g. at port) is required in order to assess the multimodal functionalities of the use case

5. Location for lab trials, and high-level description of the type of tests to be performed

Location for lab trials: CTTC Lab Barcelona

Two UC scenarios are identified of interest and are under investigation to be tested and validated in CTTC Lab in Barcelona.

Scenario 1: Multimodal network slice prediction, negotiation and management for passengers and freight when crossing borders

Service level functionalities:

- Traffic estimation (to dimension allocated resources)
- Service differentiation based on ongoing services (eMBB vs uRLLC, mMTC)

5G functionalities to be tested and demonstrated:

- Generation of Network slice requests based on the actual and predicted cross-border vertical requirements
- Network slice creation, deployment and management
- Network slice negotiation between: a) two neighbouring PLMNs; b) verticals and PLMNs

KPIs to be demonstrated and validated:

- QoS degradation < 5% during cross-border mobility
- Zero dropped sessions during cross-border mobility
- Low slice deployment time

Scenario 2: Multimodal automated border control for passengers and freight

Service level functionalities:

- Risk assessment based on AI/ML analysis of cargo data, license plate, cross-reference of info, etc
- Preparation of multimodal transfer through the exchange of information (ETA, slice pre-allocation)
- Authorities interaction (customs)

5G functionalities to be tested and demonstrated:

- Real time analysis and prediction of border conditions on two sides of the borders. The outcome of this analysis is the generation of requests for network slice establishment on both PLMNs to support the means of border control.
- Establishment of appropriate network slices on both PLMNs for the communication between the means of border control (cameras, sensors etc.) and the Customs servers
- Possible migration of selected custom services from Cloud to MEC in case of special situations or emergencies
- Establishment of inter-PLMN Network slice for the communication between the two border Customs.

KPIs to be demonstrated and validated:

- Low slice deployment time
- Increase of operational efficiency of customs/borders authorities
- Decrease of security incidents in cross-border areas

6. Location for large-scale trials (both localized and large-scale)

Via Baltica North

7. Logging of data: please specify if data of all equipment (from point 3.) will be logged. If not, or if timing synchronization issues (e.g. with smartphones) are expected, please indicate

- Data from the OBU, RSU, smartphone(s) and Cloud/Edge server will be logged for this use case, including the attached sensors (where applicable)
- Data shippers will be developed for the collection of logs and delivery to a platform for further processing.
- A platform will be used (e.g. ELK Stack) for aggregating the logs from all the involved sensors and applications, analysing these logs, and create visualizations for testing, validation and demonstration purposes.

- If a project wise common data model will be become available, the UC will adopt this data model, otherwise a custom fixed data logging format will be implemented to facilitate the post-processing of results.
- Where necessary, data encryption and anonymization will be implemented to increase the security and privacy of data and to guarantee compliance with GDPR.
- NTP servers will be used for timing synchronization among the different components of the use case

8. User involvement: please indicate how end users (such as general public, or employees) will be involved in the trials, and how information from end users will be collected.

End users such as professional and/or private drivers, as well as pedestrians (e.g. travellers, customs agents) will take part in the use case testing/trials and will interact with the developed user interface (via laptops and/or smartphones). For confidentiality and ease of access purposes the people involved in the trials will be preferably employed by one of the project partners. A clear and understandable consent form will be provided to the human experimenters informing them about the data to be logged. Data logging follows GDPR guidelines and is anonymized to protect the privacy of the human experimenters. No specific information regarding each user will be collected besides their location (GPS data from smartphone or vehicle) and potential video recordings of the tests.

6.5.3 UC5.3 FRMCS telemetry operation

1. Use Case

The main goal of use case 5.3 is to test 5G instead of GSM-R for ERTMS as a transport technology (Figure 35).

The second part is the cross-border handover procedure from one railway operator ERTMS system to another. What interests in this case is the time needed to register train on new ERTMS system (Figure 36). First delay can occur with 5G network change LMT/Telia. Second delay is due to train registration on new ERTMS system after border crossing. Both these times together form an overall delay and influence possible train speed and overall safety.

Third part is the direct connection between in-train ETCS equipment and 5G-enabled railway signalling devices (further – RSD) in case connection to ERTMS server is interrupted (Figure 37). This also is valid in case handover process takes too long time. As of today, such systems do not exist and are made theoretically and practically possible with 5G feature of direct M2M connectivity. Possibly, this feature of ETCS-RSD communication will have to be developed.

Figure 35. Use of 5G instead of GSM-R in ERTMS level 2 & 3 systems.

Figure 36. Handover between different ERTMS systems for trains crossing the border.

Figure 37. Direct M2M communication in case network connection with central system is down

2. Partners involved and their roles

- Development:
 - o <TBA>: 5G-enabled ERTMS equipment research, development, prototyping
- Network:
 - o Telia, LMT: network provider
- Testing:
 - o <TBA>: developers' equipment test results, requirements and/or expectations
 - o TTU: pre-instalment equipment testing
 - o EVR (AS Eesti Raudtee): railway infrastructure, ERTMS back-end, work organization and management
 - o PV (Pasažieru Vilčiens): train engine with test equipment
 - o <TBA>: ERTMS back-end on Latvian side

3. Equipment needed for the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors) and providers.

- Train engine with 5G-enabled ETCS equipment on-board
- Compatible ERTMS control centre
- 5G-enabled RSD (semaphores, railroad crossing barriers, interlocking)
- Analyzer for handover latency detection

4. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g. closed roads, roads with multiple lanes).

- Latvia-Estonia train border crossing has to be arranged and confirmed by the authorities
- Train-installed ETCS and operated ERTMS as well as RSD systems have to be compatible (R&D side responsibility)

5. Location for lab trials, and high-level description of the type of tests to be performed

- Tallinn: before installing ETCS, RSD and ERTMS equipment, they will have to be tested for compatibility and interoperability. Initial testing: basic connectivity ETCS-5G-ERTMS, RSD-5G-ERTMS, ETCS-5G-RSD in lab environment.

6. Location for large-scale trials (both localized and large-scale)

- All trials to be done in Valga-Valka region

7. Logging of data: please specify if data of all equipment (from point 3.) will be logged. If not, or if timing synchronization issues (e.g. with smartphones) are expected, please indicate

- Data collected during handover from ETCS, ERTMS, RSD will have timestamp
- All alarms, errors, notifications, that could arise during any of the trials in any of the systems (ETCS, ERTMS, RSD) to be logged.
- Full normal behaviour logs not to be included in the report.

8. User involvement: please indicate how end users (such as general public, or employees) will be involved in the trials, and how information from end users will be collected.

- End users are not involved in any of the tests as no end-user devices to be tested.

7 Conclusions

This deliverable provides an overview of the testing framework. At the moment of writing (end of November), the specifications of the use cases, the test network deployment and the KPIs are still under development.

The nature of the CCAM use cases puts stringent requirements to the testing environment, like a closed traffic environment with multiple lanes covered by multiple networks, allowing to test handover manoeuvres. At the moment of writing, the selection of the places suitable to trial cross-border CCAM scenarios is still ongoing.

The technical validation will be performed in 3 cycles: two localized trials, for 3GPP R16 and R17, as well as a large-scale trial on the corridor Riga-Valga-Tallinn-Helsinki. Part of the trials, especially CCAM use cases, will be performed as short duration test sessions, whereas some use cases can be trialled in naturalistic Living Lab scenarios.

Based on an initial list of the KPIs, the data, which have to be logged, are defined. At the network side, both use case agnostic data will be collected, as well as use-case specific data. Most of the use case specific data will be collected at the applications. The applications hence have to implement the required logging for being able to calculate the KPIs. In addition all network elements have to be synchronised with each other, in order to be able to measure latencies accurately.

Data collection tools will be developed to import the data in the Tenant Web. Data has to be imported both for the CCAM use cases, performed in short duration test sessions, and the Living Lab use cases. Tools may also be required to synchronise the starting and ending of logging at the different components during the test sessions.

In order to be able to import the data of all use cases in the Tenant Web, the data of all use cases should be stored in a uniform format, which has to be agreed in the following months. The data collection procedures are briefly included in this report and will be further elaborated in the Data Management Plan (Deliverable D7.5) by M6.

The test framework will be refined in the coming months, based on the finalised specifications of the use cases and the definition of the KPIs and their measurements. The updated version of the test framework and the logging format will be described in the next version of this deliverable.

8 References

- [1] 5G Infrastructure Association (2020, June) Business Validation in 5G-PPP vertical use cases. Retrieved from https://5g-ppp.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/5G_White_paper_Business-validation-v1.0a.pdf
- [2] Deming, W. Edwards (1986). Out of the crisis. Cambridge, MA: Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Center for Advanced Engineering Study.
- [3] 5G-SOLUTIONS, 5G - solutions for European Citizens, <https://www.5gsolutionsproject.eu/>
- [4] 5G-TOURS, <https://5gtours.eu/>
- [5] 5G-EVE, 5G European Validation platform for Extensive trials, <https://www.5g-eve.eu/>
- [6] 5G-MOBIX, Driving forward Connected & Automated Mobility, <https://www.5g-mobix.com/>
- [7] FESTA Handbook, Version 7 (2018, December), Retrieved from <https://connectedautomateddriving.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/FESTA-Handbook-Version-7.pdf>
- [8] TRUSTS, Trusted Secure Data Sharing Space, <https://www.trusts-data.eu/>
- [9] Kosmatos, E. et al. (2020), 5G-TOURS D7.1 Evaluation Methodology, Retrieved from <http://5gtours.eu/documents/deliverables/D7.1.pdf>
- [10] Filippou, A. (2020) TRUSTS D2.4 Methodologies for the technological/ business validation of use case results,
- [11] ITU-P.800.1 (07/2016) Series P: Terminals and Subjective and Objective Assessment Methods - Methods for objective and subjective assessment of speed and video quality - Mean opinion score (MOS) methodology
- [12] Boleguin, P, Nesse, P-J, Lonsethagen, H. (2019), 5G-SOLUTIONS, D1.4A Methodologies for the validation of 5G and for LL measurements (v1.0), <https://www.5gsolutionsproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Deliverable-D1.4A-Methodologies-for-the-validation-of-5G-and-for-LL-measurements-v1-WIT-Final.pdf>
- [13] ISO/IEC 9646 Information technology – Open Systems Interconnection – Conformance testing methodology and framework, <https://www.iso.org/standard/17473.html>
- [14] Tzanettis K. et al. (2020) 5G-SOLUTIONS, D3.1B, KPI Visualisation System Specifications and Design (v2.0), Retrieved from https://www.5gsolutionsproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/D3_1B_KPI_Visualisation_System_Specifications_and_Design_v2.7_28Apr2020-APPART.pdf
- [15] CBS Insights (2019) The Top 20 Reasons Startups Fail, CBINSIGHTS, Retrieved from: <https://www.cbinsights.com/research/startup-failure-reasons-top/>
- [16] The Lean Startup (n.d.) Methodology, Retrieved from: <http://theleanstartup.com/principles>
- [17] Still, K. (2017) Accelerating Research Innovation by Adopting the Lean Startup Paradigm. Technology Innovation Management Review, 7(5): 32-43. <http://doi.org/10.22215/timreview/1075>
- [18] Macharis C., Verbeke A., De Brucker K. (2004) The strategic evaluation of new technologies through Multicriteria analysis: the Advisors case, In: Bekiaris, E., Nakanishi Y. (Eds.), Economic Impacts of Intelligent Transportation Systems: Innovations and Case Studies. Research in Transportation Economics. Elsevier, Vol. 8, pp. 443–462.
- [19] K. Katsaros et al. (2019) 5G-MOBIX D2.5, Initial evaluation KPIs and metrics. Retrieved from <https://www.5g-mobix.com/assets/files/5G-MOBIX-D2.5-Initial-evaluation-KPIs-and-metrics-V1.4.pdf>
- [20] 5G for Europe: An Action Plan. European Commission, SWD (2016), 306.
- [21] European Commission (2019), STRIA Roadmap on Connected and Automated Transport: Road, Rail and Waterborne, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation.
- [22] Brooke, J. (1996). SUS: A 'Quick and Dirty' Usability Scale. In P. Jordan, B. Thomas, I. McClelland, & B. Weerdmeester (Eds.), Usability Evaluation In Industry (pp. 189-194). London: CRC Press
- [23] Schrepp, M., Hinderks, A., & Thomaschewski, J. r. (2017). Construction of a Benchmark for the User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ). International Journal of Interactive Multimedia and Artificial Intelligence, 4(Regular Issue), 40-44. doi:10.9781/ijimai.2017.445.

- [24] Dehn, D. M. (2008). Assessing the Impact of Automation on the Air Traffic Controller: The SHAPE Questionnaires. *Air Traffic Control Quarterly*, 16(2), 127-146. doi:10.2514/atcq.16.2.127.
- [25]Kaan, J. (2017). "User Acceptance of Autonomous Vehicles: Factors and Implications", M.S. thesis, Delft University of Technology, Delft, Netherlands.
- [26]Davis, F. (1985). A technology acceptance model for empirically testing new end-user information systems – theory and results, PhD thesis, Massachusetts Institute of Technology.
- [27]Venkatesh, V., Morris, M. G., Davis, G. B., and Davis, F. D. (2003). User acceptance of information technology: Toward a unified view. *MIS quarterly*, 425-478
- [28]Van Der Laan, J. D., Heino, A., & De Waard, D. (1997). A simple procedure for the assessment of acceptance of advanced transport telematics. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 5(1), 1-10. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0968-090X\(96\)00025-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0968-090X(96)00025-3)
- [29]On the Road to Automated Mobility: An EU Strategy for Mobility of the Future. European Commission COM (2018) 283.